

The logo features a green line-art icon above the word 'PROBONO'. The icon depicts a stylized building with a tree on the left and a cloud on the right, connected by a network of lines. The word 'PROBONO' is written in a bold, green, sans-serif font.

PROBONO

D2.5 Collaborative engagement tools, stakeholder innovation (FINAL)

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*The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient
buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods*

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 ⁵ Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001/2018/2001

and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AU	Aarhus University
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Secretariat
QM	Quality Management
SC	Scientific Coordinator
TMT	Technical Management Team
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
UCD	University College Dublin
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

This report offers information related to IT tools adopted within PROBONO's Living Labs and their Social Innovation activities. It explores the lessons learnt from the adoption of selected tools and how they could be adapted for implementation in future activities from PROBONO and beyond the project's completion. Furthermore, it provides resources and insights about the choices of tools, their benefits and limitations, according to engagement and collaboration needs.

The relevance of this is related to finding ways to support engagement activities, so they are inclusive and attractive to stakeholders, so users and citizens not only understand the transformations that are proposed but also feel invited to interact and to contribute with their ideas and perspectives. A significant part of participatory processes is to promote meaningful engagement, empowering communities so their inputs are taken into consideration. This, however, is not always easy and can be developed using different frameworks and strategies.

For a better apprehension of the possibilities for applying IT tools, this delivery identifies a range of available IT tools, in a general overview. Later, it provides details on key IT tools that have been tested in PROBONO's activities and can be considered for adoption across all of the project's Living Labs. Further on it presents the context of each Living Lab, and how partners adopted their set of tools, informing its benefits, limitations and how some of those tools can be integrated into the PROBONO Digital Twin and in community-host platforms, when feasible.

Finally, it points to the findings and the lessons learnt regarding the adoption of IT tools for collaborative engagement, considering different needs and phases of the PROBONO Project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T2.4. IT Collaborative engagement tools for holistic and multi-stakeholder innovation [M12-M36]	<p>ST2.4.1. Collaborative Engagement Tools</p> <p>Select tools for both stakeholder engagement in LLs and agile customer centric innovation and implementation strategies for PROBONO innovations. Identify already existing and/or are currently used in Living Labs. Perform trials and tests for selection. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p> <p>ST2.4.2. Localisation and adaptation of Collaborative Engagement Tools</p> <p>Identify required localisation or adaptation of tools and plan and implement LL deployment; link tools to the PROBONO LL digital twin through standardised APIs. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p> <p>ST2.4.3. Neighbourhood sustainability platform</p> <p>Parametrise and explore the feasibility of the integration of collaborative engagement tools into host community-facing platforms (such as websites) of relevant partner organisations. This subtask will also direct the integration and implementation. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p>	D2.4	D2.4 sets a baseline for IT Collaborative tools and is directly related to D2.5.
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D2.5: Collaborative engagement tools for multi-stakeholder innovation (FINAL)</p> <p>This report formulates the findings of T2.4, and explores step/s B) Perform adaptation and localisation, interface APIs and Parametrisation. [B=M36] (PU)</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The aim of this document is to present IT collaborative engagement tools that have been selected and used across the PROBONO Living Labs. It also provides information of how certain tools could be further adopted by the Living Labs in the cases where it could support innovative activities. From this, the present deliverable explores possible localisation and adaptation of the tools, specifically related on how they can be integrated to PROBONO's Digital Twin and HMI

Platform through standardised APIs. Finally, the document explores the feasibility of integrating the tools and/or their outputs into host community-facing platforms within each Living Lab.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPS/Deliverables

This document builds on the work of Deliverable 2.4, which focused on understanding what IT collaborative tools are currently being used by each Living Lab and researching other tools which might be useful. In Deliverable 2.5, there is a focus on the advantages and challenges for IT collaborative tools and which tools each Living Lab has selected for use in their GBN. This Deliverable sits in Work Package 2, and the work carried out will also be reflected in Deliverable 8.9, which focuses on capacity building in each Living Lab. This Deliverable is the final submission for T2.4.

1.4 Contribution to creating GBN

IT tools have the main purpose of facilitating engagement and co-creation in multiple ways, thus promoting important discussions among a range of stakeholders. By using such tools within different types of engagement activities, these diverse groups will have an enhanced opportunity to create a shared vision regarding their understanding of a GBN. This shared vision has the potential to consider each context's needs and desires while also contributing to a broader concept of a GBN.

2 IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

2.1 Collaborative Engagement

2.1.1 Definition and relevance

Closely aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals, Horizon 2020 projects such as PROBONO, aim to achieve a better quality of life for citizens, whilst adapting cities into a climate transition framework, with more sustainable infrastructure and more just environments (Gohari et al., 2020). Overall, citizen engagement is critical to the public debate, delivery or management of public services and goods, in a way that ensures policy and actions are responsive to communities, especially the most vulnerable groups (World Bank, 2016).

The implementation of sustainable urban innovations within the smart-city approach has increasingly turned to a citizen-centric perspective, after previous experience demonstrated that not engaging properly with communities can lead to a technocratic and instrumental attitude, tending to be unsuccessful (Borsboom-van Beurden et al., 2017; Cardullo & Kitchin, 2019). According to such critiques, when engagement is insufficient in smart-city initiatives, they tend to reproduce the logic of a neoliberal form of urban management and development; also, the perception from the communities is that technology is being used to discipline and control citizens (Cardullo & Kitchin, 2019). Significantly, the common use of words such as “customers”, “users” or “consumers” in the smart innovations debate impacts relations of power, implying a one-way transactional relationship, that is, attributing aspects of sustainable challenges, e.g., energy consumption, solely to individuals a responsibility that is, in fact, collective and shared among different groups of stakeholders (Coy et al., 2021). These challenges are especially present in the climate transition because in many cases infrastructure change is still driven by centralised, top-down practices, regulatory framework and institutional structures, making citizens feel “locked-out” of the decision-making processes and disconnected from systems that are present in their every-day lives (Mee et al., 2021).

2.1.2 Advantages and challenges of collaborative engagement

Alternatively, when communities are actively engaged, they often play a critical role in transformations, being empowered to critically promote real access to the climate transition

benefits, from a democratic, just and citizen-centric point of view (Coy et al., 2021). In other words, meaningful participation, involving citizens in co-designing solutions as non-experts in technical knowledge, but experts in their own community, can increase democratic governance, productivity, trust in the climate transition process and in government, transparency and citizen satisfaction (Gohari et al., 2020; Halachmi & Holzer, 2010).

The advantages of citizen participation can be such as the fact that when citizens are involved, they can better understand difficulties and become experts in matters relevant to their city. Also, public servants learn about the reasons that can make a certain policy unpopular and how to think about alternatives to citizens' contributions (Simonofski et al., 2019).

Despite its critical role, there are important challenges to citizen participation in practice. More than involving only citizens "directly affected" by a plan or project, citizen engagement should be broadly inclusive, making sure groups involved in the processes are representative of the population, to avoid, for example, problems related to bias, as some of the engaged groups could have preconceived ideas towards the people who will be affected by the smart city implementation (Ampatzidou et al., 2018; Simonofski et al., 2019). By being aware of this, PROBONO LL leaders can take measures to mitigate and compensate for it, especially for avoiding underrepresentation from particular groups. Another key aspect is that participating can be very demanding in terms of effort, time and cost, both from the organisers and the participants' perspectives. Many times the motivation to engage is reduced if activities are too demanding, as individuals tend to prioritise spending their time in leisure or in actions that have a high personal relevance (Hassan & Hamari, 2020). In this sense, IT tools can be used to address challenges of time and complexity involved in many approaches, making activities and events accessible, easy and engaging, by using features such as e-voting, negotiation, gamification and crowdsourcing (Hassan & Hamari, 2020; Simonofski et al., 2019)ⁱ.

2.1.3 IT tools for Collaborative Engagement

The use of IT tools should be planned considering both the highlights and limitations of their features, being conjugated with other relevant factors and options. Besides, despite the possibility of financial compensation for participants in some cases, it is very important to consider the time and alternatives for meetings, regarding different groups that exist in that context, especially more vulnerable ones such as commuters, people who are dependent on public transport, care takers / single parents, night shift workers, students, elderly and low-

income groups. Nonetheless, if used alone IT tools can restrict participation for groups with limited familiarity or access to internet technologies (Simonofski et al., 2019).

2.2 IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

This section provides a list of IT tools that are suitable for collaborative engagement within a GBN, as an overview of what is available from a broad perspective. Further on shortlist of tools is presented as being relevant for adoption and integration in all PROBONO's Living Labs. These tools were chosen for their potential in supporting innovative activities for social engagement and behavioural change during the project and beyond its completion.

2.2.1 Overview of available tools

As an overview of the available tools, the following table (Table 1) presents and organises them by needs, approach and examples of specific tools. This table was initiated for D2.4, starting from a desktop search and was updated in collaboration with PROBONO's WP2 partners along with the discussions for Social Innovation Activities. It includes tools that can help implement citizen and user engagement in different approaches, considering distinct phases of the engagement processes during the project. As there are multiple technological resources available, it is important to note it is not an extensive list in the sense that there might be other IT tools that have not been identified or discussed during the project so far. The full table, containing further explanation about the tools is in the Appendix 01.

Need	Approach	IT Collaborative Engagement Tools
Co-production of knowledge and collective understanding	Participatory mapping and storytelling	Geosurvey
		Survey 123
		Open Street Maps
		Maptionnaire
	Storytelling	Story Maps
Tools for engagement and decision making	Co-creation processes	Geodesign
		Minecraft
		Hackathons
	Online voting	Helios Voting
		Agora voting / nVotes
		eBallot
	Online workshops	Miro Board
Etherpad		
Mural		
Testing	Serious games and gamification	Minecraft
		Urban Nature Explorer
		SuperBarrio
		NegoDesign
	Prototyping	Beta Projects
Facilitating continuing engagement	Education and communication	Newsletters
		Social Networks
	Scaling up	Waypoint
		Change X
Integration of engagement tools	Suites	Consul
		Decidim
		Delib Citizen Space

Table 1: List of IT Tools by needs and approaches

2.2.2 Relevant IT tools for PROBONO's Living Labs

From the discussions within the Living Labs, their activities and the findings so far, some tools are identified as relevant for implementation in engagement. In some cases, they already were implemented or are planned to be adopted across all Living Labs (e.g., CERNA Survey, Placemaking Fresk). Others have been implemented and tested in some of the Living Labs (e.g., StoryMaps, CartoSpot) and are presented as suggestions for their potential in achieving the goals established for the PROBONO project and will be further considered for the final phases of the project.

Placemaking Fresk

Placemaking Fresk is not a digital tool per se, but a workshop framework that adopts digital tools and can provide relevant inputs. It is being developed by SIN and MM, and it is based on the well-known Climate Fresk approach, which is an innovative co-creation workshop to facilitate the understanding of climate challenges. The Placemaking Fresk offers a similar strategy, focusing in urban planning and community engagement, building a visual representation of a sustainable city. Designed to be accessible to everyone, this tool uses the ISO37101 standard to help participants in building a comprehensive view of their city or neighbourhood by using a set of cards. These cards represent different urban elements: mobility, energy, housing, and more, supporting participants in understanding the complexity of urban sustainability while identifying potential solutions for improving their area. When displaying the cards and drawing links between them, participants can visualise the links between systems (e.g., how green spaces affect both health and climate change, or how transport choices can influence air quality, health and social equality).

Figure 1: Tailored cards prepared for each workshop, considering the GBN's strategic view and current projects

Figure 2: Tailored cards prepared for each workshop, considering the GBN's strategic view and current projects

The primary objective of the Placemaking Fresk is to foster collaborative thinking and problem-solving among diverse stakeholders in urban development, covering various aspects such as governance, education, health, and environmental sustainability. Participants work together to:

- Analyse the current state of their urban environment;
- Identify challenges and opportunities;
- Develop potential solutions aligned with sustainability principles;
- Create a shared vision for their city or neighbourhood.

		12 Issues											
		Governance	Education	Innovation	Health and care in the community	Culture and community identity	Living together	Sustainable production and consumption	Living environment and working	Safety and security	City and community infrastructures	Mobility	Biodiversity and Ecosystem services
6 Purposes	Attractiveness												
	Well-being												
	Social cohesion												
	Resilience												
	Preservation and improvement of environment												
	Responsible resources use												

Figure 3: Structure of the map used during the workshop, allowing participants to identify the multiple impact areas one activity, can have as well as synergies across different activities.

One of the key strengths of the Placemaking Fresk is that it can be an online or in-person workshop. When in-person, it is possible to implement the Placemaking Fresk without digital tools. In this case, the resources would be such as large paper sheets, sticky notes, and markers. When online, the Placemaking Fresk can be done with the support of web-based collaborative platforms, such as Miro or Mural. These digital whiteboarding tools provide a virtual space for participants to engage in the workshop activities remotely. The online format offers relevant advantages that should be considering when planning the activity:

- Increased accessibility for participants;
- Real-time collaboration and idea sharing;
- Easy documentation of workshop outputs.

As a web-based tool, the Placemaking Fresk relies on the hosting platform's infrastructure and privacy policies. When using platforms like Miro or Mural, user accounts are typically required for participation. However, the tool itself does not store or track individual user data beyond the workshop session. This means that once users leave the board, there is no track of individual contributions, ensuring a level of anonymity in the final output. This approach helps to protect user privacy while still allowing for meaningful collaboration during the workshop.

The primary output of the Placemaking Fresk is the collaborative Miro or Mural board created during the workshop. This captures the collective insights, ideas, and proposed solutions generated by the participants. While the board itself does not automatically generate reports, facilitators can use it as a basis to create synthesis documents in PDF or Word format for the participants and other stakeholders.

There is a relevant potential for integrating the Placemaking Fresk or its outputs into a Digital Twin but this is yet unsure within the PROBONO project. While the collaborative insights generated during the workshops could inform or enhance a Digital Twin of GBNs, direct integration requires further discussions.

So far SIN and MM have been developing the tool and working in mapping PROBONO items, creating the forementioned card game. They also have adopted this approach to develop Paris Participatory Budget. The workshop methodology is currently under design, with aims to enhance it through tests with early adopters (PROBONO partners and external). There's also the

idea of replicating it with at least one community and then with the wider consortium partners in the next GA.

For presenting an easy, innovative and dynamic way of collaboration between stakeholders, the tool can potentially be used beyond the completion of PROBONO, within its Living Labs and also in other locations. In conclusion, the Placemaking Fresk represents a valuable addition to the toolkit of urban planners, community organizers, and local governments. By combining the structured approach with the flexibility of both analogue and digital settings, it offers a powerful way of engaging communities in shaping the future of their urban environments.

StoryMaps

StoryMaps is an online storytelling platform for presenting projects and for promoting engagement with the public. Developed by ArcGIS, it enables the communication of complex information sets in an accessible and visually appealing way. The platform is basically a website that allows users – e.g., PROBONO’s partners - to create narratives, combining different elements, such as maps, 3D scenes, embedded content, videos, photos, text, and audio [10]. The platform's flexibility supports the creation of stories that effectively communicate activities and can also be adopted to support whole projects or set of Living Lab’s initiatives.

Among the features of Storymaps is the possibility of creating customised maps in a quick and easy way, which is particularly useful for PROBONO’s partners and the LLs contexts, where location-specific information is critical for understanding the GBN’s challenges and possibilities. Additionally, the platform can integrate other tools such as surveys and geosurveys, which has been adopted in PROBONO’s Geodesign Workshops for Dublin and Aarhus, as further detailed in this report. In these cases, Storymaps was used for creating dedicated landing page for each activity, providing a narrative and also a step-by-step guide for the event. Furthermore, it can also include the results of such events in visually appealing dashboards, becoming a comprehensive dataset about engagement activities and more.

10 <https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-storymaps/overview>

Common ground: Campus, Community and Climate 📄 ...

Introduction Geodesign Workshop Belfield Campus Survey Sites of interest History of UCD Belfield Campus Commons & →

The Outcomes

Anonymously collected information will help students develop ideas for reimagining UCD's edges in 2050, shaping hypothetical sustainable solutions. These outcomes, part of a learning exercise, will contribute to end-of-year portfolios. Results will be presented publicly and shared with Dun Laoghaire County Council as part of the EU project PROBONO which is a partnership with UCD School of Architecture and Environmental Policy.

For further information on outcomes and data usage see [here](#).

Probono an EU Project

The PROBONO project envisions to establish a people-focused European construction industry, by working in harmony with the...

<https://www.probonoh2020.eu>

How do I take part?

The workshop is in partnership with Open House Dublin. **Registration is essential**, so if you haven't registered please do so now through [their website](#).

Figure 4: StoryMaps page elaborated for Dublin LL's Geodesign Workshop in October 2024.

(<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/39906892a0ae45f19d044227fee770e0>)

The platform allows that the created stories can be shared in various ways, including as standalone narratives or as part of collections [11]. This allows users to adapt their content distribution strategy to different audiences and purposes. As such the content can be embedded within websites and shared in social media platforms. This is particularly relevant for Living Labs looking to extend its reach and engage with the wider public. Moreover, StoryMaps offers analytics tools that provide clear insights into audience engagement, so partners can refine their communication strategies and measure impacts.

In conclusion, ArcGIS StoryMaps is a valuable IT tool for collaborative engagement providing a user-friendly interface and interesting features make it potentially very useful for PROBONO Living Labs to present their initiatives and to engage with participants.

11 <https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-storymaps/overview>

CartoSpot

This geo-survey platform has been developed by UCD researcher Dr. José P. Gómez Barrón S. It is an innovative map-based participation engagement IT tool that has emerged as a powerful way for enhancing collaboration and dialogue among diverse stakeholders, particularly from communities.

Figure 5: CartoSpot “Meitheal Mapping” page, tailored for Dublin’s Geodesign Workshop in 2024.
(<https://meitheal.cartospot.com/page/about-this-map>)

The primary objective of CartoSpot is to create an interoperable, inclusive, and user-friendly map-based participatory platform. The tool is designed to simplify the process of collaborative and open mapping, making it accessible to a wide range of users regardless of their technical expertise. Considering PROBONO’s initiatives, the following functionalities of the platform can be considered for integrating it into the project’s initiatives across most of the Living Labs.

- **Data Collection:** CartoSpot enables the collection of ground-level data, local knowledge, and insights, very useful for gathering diverse perspectives and information from community members.
- **Spatial Collaboration:** The map-based interface allows users to interact with and contribute to spatial data, fostering a shared understanding of geographic contexts.

- **Community Engagement:** By providing a platform for dialogue and collaboration, CartoSpot facilitates active participation in community-related projects and decision-making processes.

Discussions are ongoing between PROBONO partners and the tool developer to understand how the outputs of CartoSpot could be integrated into the Digital Twin.

In conclusion, CartoSpot can be a strategic tool for PROBONO's LLs to collaborative engagement and mapping within their GBNs.

CERNA Survey

As presented in D2.6, CERNA was developed as an assessment tool, to map out existing knowledge, misconceptions, social norms and attitudes towards the climate and energy crisis. PROBONO Living Labs are situated in diverse climate zones, with important variations between their building typologies, as well as diverse heating and cooling systems. Because of this, there was a need to develop Such setting offered the need and opportunity to run country-specific analysis, which is detailed in D2.6 and outlined in the Living Labs' activities described in the present report. The overall strategy of the CERNA Survey has two aims: to address pluralistic ignorance and to address misconceptions about individual actions' impact.

Within PROBONO, the survey has been done in Madrid and Porto LLs, and it is under planning for the others. Post-survey, communication pieces are elaborated, and these interventions focus on citizens and policymakers, raising awareness and informing about social norms. By identifying misconceptions about climate and their impact on various behaviours, the study will educate and inform Living Lab citizens about actions they can individually make for a positive impact on a larger scale. As presented in D2.6, a draft of a poster below presents three key messages:

- You are not alone, the majority of your co-citizens share your climate relevant beliefs and concerns
- This is what to do
- How to change behaviours

YOU'RE PART OF A BIG, SUPPORTIVE WAVE!

THINK YOU'RE ONE OF THE FEW WHO CARE ABOUT THE CLIMATE CRISIS? THINK AGAIN! **74% OF MADRID CITIZENS ARE WORRIED ABOUT CLIMATE CHANGE, AND 82% BACK GREEN POLICIES.** IT'S CALLED A "FALSE SOCIAL REALITY"—WHERE WE THINK WE'RE IN THE MINORITY, BUT WE'RE REALLY NOT. SO, IF YOU FEEL LIKE YOU'RE SWIMMING AGAINST THE TIDE, HERE'S THE GOOD NEWS: YOU'RE NOT!

FOLLOW THE QR CODE TO LEARN MORE ABOUT FALSE SOCIAL REALITIES!

BUT DO YOU KNOW HOW TO SWIM?

WE KNOW YOU CARE, BUT **DO YOU KNOW WHAT REALLY MAKES A DIFFERENCE?** MANY OF US AREN'T SURE! WHILE TURNING OFF THE LIGHTS IS IMPORTANT, DID YOU KNOW THAT:

- TAKING 2-MINUTE SHORTER SHOWERS IS UP TO 2.5 TIMES MORE IMPACTFUL?**
- TURNING DOWN THE THERMOSTAT AND PUTTING ON A JUMPER IS 20 TIMES MORE IMPACTFUL?**
- BIKING TO WORK IS 80 TIMES MORE IMPACTFUL?**

FOLLOW THE QR CODE FOR AN EXTENDED LIST OF ACTIONS WE CAN TAKE FOR A GREENER FUTURE!

LET'S SWIM TOGETHER/HERE IS HOW TO START SWIMMING

IN A BUSY LIFE, IT IS HARD TO CHANGE OUR BEHAVIOURS AND DO WHAT WE KNOW IS RIGHT. IT REQUIRES WILLPOWER, BUT MORE SO, **IT TAKES DESIGN AND PLANNING!** BY MAKING SMALL CHANGES IN YOUR OWN ENVIRONMENT YOU CAN SET YOURSELF UP FOR SUCCESS AND CREATE THE CHANGES YOU WISH!

- CONTEXT: MAKE THE RIGHT THING EASY** AND THE WRONG THING HARD
- REPETITION: REPEAT, REPEAT REPEAT** AND PLAN FOR WHEN YOU FAIL
- REWARDS: INTRINSIC REWARDS** WORK BETTER THAN CHOCOLATE

FOLLOW THE QR CODE TO LEARN HOW

SCAN ME

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101037075. This output reflects only the author's view, and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Table 2: First draft of a CERNA poster, presented in D2.6

The poster or communication material presents then a QR code that leads to a section of the PROBONO website with more in-depth materials and country-specific information.

Although the CERNA survey is not a digital tool in itself, it provides important outputs that will be incorporated into communication pieces in close collaboration with WP8. Significantly, it can be integrated into the Digital Twin and its HMI, with ongoing discussions across PROBONO's partners, considering interactive dashboards and maps.

3 IT Collaborative Engagement tools in the Living Labs

3.1 Dublin

3.1.1 Planned activities

2024 Geodesign Workshop

The Common Ground workshop, hosted by University College Dublin (UCD) on October 19, 2024, was a pivotal event within the broader framework of the EU-funded PROBONO project, which aims to create Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs) as models of sustainable urban development across Europe. The workshop's primary objective was to evaluate and demonstrate the potential of Geodesign as a tool for multi-stakeholder engagement, particularly in transforming UCD's campus environment to foster stronger connections with its surrounding communities. With a vision set for 2050, this event engaged a diverse group of participants—including UCD researchers, architecture students, local community members, and city officials—in a day-long collaborative session focused on developing proposals for enhancing campus accessibility and interaction with adjacent neighbourhoods. In the Appendix 02 there is a complete material about this activity.

Throughout the workshop, participants employed Geodesign tools and methods to analyse six key sites around the UCD campus. This process facilitated discussions that reflected the unique needs, aspirations, and perspectives of the different stakeholders involved.

By collaborating in this way, the workshop sought to address several specific objectives:

- (1)** To create a platform for students and community members to exchange ideas, co-design solutions, and explore transformative design projects;
- (2)** To activate underutilized campus spaces, envisioning them as hubs for interaction, creativity, and community engagement; and
- (3)** To establish a resilient network of individuals and groups committed to advancing sustainability and climate resilience across campus and local communities.

The preparatory process encompassed all activities developed in advance of the Geodesign Workshop. This stage included several key elements:

Stage 1

Preliminary Lectures: As part of the 2nd-year design studio, students attended preliminary lectures on UCD's history to build a foundational understanding of the campus and its surrounding context. Before these lectures, surveys were distributed to local residents to gather insights, understand community interests, and assess potential engagement in future initiatives. All student sessions were open to the community, fostering a sense of inclusion and shared purpose within UCD.

Students were also introduced to the objectives of the Geodesign Workshop and hosted architectural studios that practiced co-design principles, preparing them for collaborative roles in the workshop.

Site Analysis: Students began analysing specific campus-edge sites, focusing on spatial and social dynamics as a foundation for the workshop's design discussions.

Stage 2

Participatory Survey (Meitheal): A survey, designed for the UCD campus community, was developed to gather insights into the stories, values, challenges, and opportunities associated with Belfield Campus.

Strategy Development: MSc Architecture, Urbanism & Climate Action students commenced work on developing strategic proposals tailored to each site, contributing to the overarching vision for campus-community integration.

Stage 3

Geodesign Workshop: An immersive and collaborative event where community members, students, and local leaders came together to reimagine UCD's campus edges through a lens of sustainability and climate resilience.

Stage 4

Feedback Survey: A brief survey was distributed to all participants, inviting them to share their thoughts and insights on the workshop experience.

Presentation for 2nd-Year Students: MSc students are expected to present the results for 2nd year students to enhance their design

Common Ground Exhibition: Connecting Campus, Community, and Climate: Participants are invited to attend an exhibition showcasing the creative solutions developed by our students. This exhibition celebrates the collaboration between campus and community, highlighting climate-resilient ideas shaped by the perspectives shared during the workshop.

Figure 6: Planning of the engagement process

Geodesign Workshop

At the start of the Geodesign workshop, participants were introduced to the workshop's purpose and the concept behind it. A brief overview of the workshop objectives was also provided.

Participants were then divided into six tables, with each table focusing on one site. Each table included two facilitators (students in this case), one community member, and additional participants, some of whom had a background with UCD or were involved in its activities.

Discussions began with each group presenting a brief overview of their strategies, covering the core ideas behind the tool and explaining what the polygons represented. This initial exchange helped participants align on the tool's purpose and gain a spatial understanding of each group's strategy.

Round 1 of discussions then commenced, where groups engaged in negotiations and initial vision development. Each group voted on the strategies they felt best aligned with their goals and addressed observed issues within UCD. While focusing on their assigned sites, they also considered the broader campus context to establish a foundation for discussion. This stage encouraged open dialogue about the strengths, challenges, and opportunities presented by the Geodesignhub tool in envisioning UCD Belfield's integration with surrounding communities.

In **Round 2**, groups advanced to developing distinct strategies for reimagining the UCD Belfield Campus. Each table prioritized site-specific elements based on the unique characteristics of their location—some sites, for instance, highlighted historical assets, while others focused on natural Afterwards, each table selected a spokesperson to share their group’s chosen priorities and reasoning features. At this stage, participants began sketching their ideas with facilitator guidance, combining the Geodesignhub polygons with their own drawings to capture a fuller vision.

Figure 7: Participants at the Geodesign Workshop.

Building negotiations

In the next phase, groups entered a negotiation process, revisiting and refining their initial strategies (Version 1). During this collaborative step, participants were encouraged to make adjustments to their proposals and, if necessary, add complementary diagrams to strengthen and clarify their design intentions.

The tables below provide a comparative overview of each group’s selections and proposals, as represented on Geodesignhub. This comparison highlights the evolving priorities, adjustments, and shared visions that emerged through the negotiation process, reflecting a collective effort to achieve a cohesive and impactful strategy for UCD Belfield Campus.

Based on their design similarities, the groups voted for the group they were likely to pair with. The groups vote as shown in the table below:

++	Definitely Yes
+	Maybe Yes
-	Maybe No
--	NEVER

Table 3: Voting ranks

Consequently, the groups were matched based on showing their interest in the other groups that presented. Groups voted for each other based on their interest and similarities while they presented their visions in round 2.

	N11	NEW	NOVA	ROE	ROSE	WOOD
N11		++	+	+	-	++
NEW	-		+	+	++	+
NOVA	-	+		-	-	++
ROE	-	++	++		-	+
ROSE	-	+	++	+		++
WOOD	+	-	++	-	++	

Table 4: Sociogram for the preparation of the coalitions

Final Design

Throughout the negotiations, groups A and B, as well as groups C and D, collaborated to debate and discuss their respective proposals. This collective effort led to the development of a refined and mutually agreed-upon strategy. The resulting negotiated strategy was then presented to the room, incorporating input from both combined pairings (A+B and C+D) as illustrated in Figure 16.

Geodesign Workshop Feedback

The input received from the participants was greatly appreciated. To gather further insights, a feedback survey was distributed to all attendees.

Overall, the participants expressed satisfaction with the tool and acknowledged its value. However, they expressed a desire for more time for discussions and recommended involving individuals from the local government. Their input underscores the importance of their perspectives and highlights the need for their active involvement in future workshops.

Conclusions

Geodesign has been demonstrated as an extremely useful approach for engaging citizens and stakeholders for an urban area, which is valuable for the PROBONO's GBNs. Among the lessons learnt are the importance of planning the activity in close collaboration with partners. Finally, although the IT tool (Geodesignhub) is quite user-friendly, it is important to have facilitators who are somewhat familiar with the it during the event; in Dublin case, these have been students from the Architecture School, who have been valuable facilitators.

2024 Open House

This year Dún Laoghaire Rathdown County Council hosted a number of venues as part of the Irish Architecture Foundation Open House Dublin 2024, Architectural Festival. One such venue was the Harbour Master's Lodge in Dún Laoghaire. This Open House event offered the public a unique glimpse into this historic building, which once served as the head office for the harbour company. Built in 1820, the lodge is a protected structure showcasing historic neoclassical architecture, crafted from Dalkey granite and crowned with a maritime clock tower and signalling turret.

At PROBONO, we are working to create a Green Building Neighbourhood in Dún Laoghaire, thanks to a collaboration between DLR County Council, University College Dublin and the European Union and other technical partners. As part of this project, we took on the task of retrofitting the windows of the Harbour Master's Lodge, whilst preserving the historical integrity of the building.

During the event, the public was presented with data analytics from the PROBONO retrofitting project aimed at enhancing the building's energy efficiency. PROBONO staff were present to explain the intricacies of retrofitting a heritage building, discussing both the obstacles encountered and the solutions found. Informative posters and handouts from both PROBONO

and SEAI provided insights into the retrofitting process and offered guidance for those interested in implementing similar interventions in their own homes. The goal of the tour was to demystify the retrofitting process, reassuring visitors that revitalizing homes and buildings, regardless of their historical architecture, is an achievable endeavour.

Over the course of the day, we welcomed a total of 120 visitors. Among them was a councillor from Bath County Council who engaged in discussions about the retrofitting process and was provided additional information to share with her team. Another notable visitor was local councillor Peter Cunningham, who offered valuable connections within the council, particularly in the planning department, to further support the project. Additionally, a family member of a former resident of the Harbour Master's Lodge shared historic photographs, enriching the cultural experience for attendees.

Overall, the Open House event was a resounding success, reflecting the community's strong interest in local heritage and history, as well as their eagerness to explore energy-efficient retrofitting options for their own homes. The event highlighted the potential for modern upgrades within historic buildings, paving the way for future projects aimed at enhancing both environmental sustainability and preserving cultural heritage.

2025 Geodesign Workshop in Dun Laoghaire Town Centre

This workshop will build on the learnings of the previous two Geodesign workshops held in Dún Laoghaire town centre and UCD and expanded to be the largest Geodesign workshop held for PROBONO.

2025 Open House

Open House 2025 will build on the success of Open House 2024 with the scope widened to include other buildings under the PROBONO Dublin LL GBN.

3.1.2 Findings

The PROBONO project has been an opportunity for DLR to advance in meaningful ways to engage citizens and to break silos. The adoption of innovative activities and tools such as

Geodesign Workshops and the demonstration of solutions through Open House brings forward important lessons for DLR staff about engagement processes. Moreover, the experiences from Dublin LL promote the identification of solutions co-created with citizens, and the IT tools that were adopted support long-term contributions.

3.1.3 Adaptation and localisation

Dublin LL Team is currently engaged in conversations about the Digital Twin integration. Preliminary ideas include interactive maps where citizens, planners and other relevant stakeholders can visualise scenarios and solutions for the Dublin GBN. This material will be elaborated from the inputs and outputs of the engagement activities. For example, in preparation for 2025 Geodesign Workshop Dublin LL will have a set of future scenarios for the area, having evaluation maps identifying risks related to different land uses or systems. For the digital twin HMI, these maps can be combined with the outputs from the 2025 Geodesign Workshop (i.e., citizens' inputs in the Cartspot and in Geodesignhub). The user could then, interact with the map, visualising how different scenarios would respond to a range of solutions.

3.1.4 Neighbourhood sustainability platform

The discussions on how to integrate the IT tools and or its outputs into community-facing platforms have been carried on, however they are in preliminary stages.

3.1.5 Conclusion

Dublin LL team has been working in testing a series of IT tools with the focus in finding ones that are suitable for meaningful collaborative engagement with citizens and for breaking silos across stakeholders of the GBN, particularly within the local authority's departments. IT tools such as Cartspot, Geodesignhub support the co-creation of GIS outputs that can be incorporated in the PROBONO Digital Twin and beyond, including the planning process of local plans. The adoption of other IT tools such as Storymaps also demonstrated to be relevant to the social innovation activities, and will be considered for the planned activities for the project 2025 final activities.

3.2 Madrid

3.2.1 Activities and IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

The activity is associated with Task 2.4, which outlined the IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods that could be used for social and behavioural innovations. The aim of Task 2.4 is to adapt and deploy collaborative engagement tools and methods such as participatory mapping and storytelling, Geodesign, virtual workshops or hackathons. The IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods used for Madrid LL are described below:

- Miro Board
- StoryMaps
- Survey 123

Crea Madrid Nuevo Norte (CREAMNN) (Formerly DCN), University College Dublin (UCD), and Social Innovation Norway (SIN) are the partners involved in the task described below.

3.2.2 Planned activities

Citizen Engagement Workshop 2023

A Citizen Engagement Workshop was held on the 15th of November 2023 in the Neighbourhood “Las Tablas” in Madrid, Spain. The workshop focused on demonstrating the outcomes that can arise from residents’ active involvement in shaping their neighbourhoods through the decision-making process. By promoting a sense of accountability and encouraging citizens to play a proactive role in driving change within their communities, the event aimed to foster unity among residents, local businesses, authorities, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), community organisations and project stakeholders. The workshop sought to empower participants and explore creative approaches to enhance neighbourhoods, ultimately contributing to developing a more vibrant and sustainable community.

StoryMap

The landing page was developed in ArcGIS StoryMap, an online storytelling platform part of ESRI, as an information portal that facilitates the project's presentation to key stakeholders. Figure 8 displays the StoryMap interface. Refer to Appendix 1 for the complete StoryMap and link.

Figure 8. Interface of StoryMap

Survey

Before starting the workshop, we utilised the ESRI tool Survey 123 to conduct an open survey, which was embedded in the StoryMap. The purpose of the survey was to collect initial data and prepare for the workshops. The survey consisted of four parts described below:

- *We want to know you (Queremos conocerte)*

This part of the survey collected general information about the participants, such as gender, age, etc.

- *We want to know how much you know about Sustainable Community Infrastructure (Queremos saber qué tanto conoces sobre las infraestructuras comunitarias sostenibles)*

This part relates to various types of energy infrastructure and their management. For each energy infrastructure, there is a brief introduction, followed by three questions about the preferred management type, location, and level of importance.

- *Priorities and concerns (Prioridades y preocupaciones)*

This part aims to understand the priorities and concerns of citizens regarding energy infrastructure. Participants were asked to identify the most beneficial infrastructure for their neighbourhood and building, and whether they would consider this when buying property. They were also asked to prioritize different types of energy.

- *We invite you to participate (Te invitamos a participar)*

This part aims to encourage citizens to join the citizens' engagement workshop by submitting their email addresses if interested.

The questions were thoughtfully crafted to assess the community's preferences and awareness levels regarding energy infrastructure. Figure 9 displays the survey interface. Refer to Appendix 2 for the complete survey.

Figure 9. Image of the first page of the Energy Community Infrastructure Survey.

Workshop

The materials used during the workshop were initially developed on the Miro board. However, due to the mature age range of the stakeholders invited, the decision was made to conduct the workshop in an analogue format. This approach aimed to mitigate potential stress among the participants.

The workshop began with a presentation about the PROBONO project and the Green Building Neighbourhoods, along with their aims and objectives. This was followed by an introduction to the workshop, a presentation of the survey results, and instructions for the workshop.

The workshop session was divided into four phases, each representing a different type of energy and its corresponding management methods. Participants worked in teams to choose the type of infrastructure they preferred and the corresponding management approach. An essential aspect of the workshop was the interactive group sessions. During these sessions, participants collaborated to discuss their viewpoints using the theoretical framework of SWOT analysis. Figure 10 presents an example of the SWOT analysis; refer to Appendix 03 for the complete material.

Figure 10. Image of the SWOT analysis.

The goal was identifying Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats at local and national levels. By evaluating the positive and negative factors that could impact the project's future development, participants were able to identify opportunities and limitations related to their respective green initiatives. Figure 11 shows the photographs taken during the workshop.

Figure 11: Work Groups during the Citizen Engagement Workshop in Madrid

During the discussions, participants learned about new technologies and green initiatives already being used in other countries and how to apply these ideas locally. Some of the topics related to green infrastructure include the development of green rooftops or rooftop gardens, renewable energy solutions, using electric vehicles, and energy-efficient heating options.

Second Citizen Engagement Initiative

Second citizen engagement initiative will take place on next spring 2026. It intends to be a participatory Codesign process to design the area located below the bridge connecting PROBONO area with the adjacent neighbourhood. Actually this area is a residual area so far and citizens participation is required to convert it into a useful space to the community. The process will take place as a workshop where actors from different stakeholders groups and interest will be invited. The codesign process will rely mainly on a digital tool, likely SuperBarrio in order to engage a broad spectrum of stakeholders, to get a higher level of engagement and to ensure inclusivity. Superbarrio is a Co-design tool that is location-specific where participants are offered a set of solutions to choose from and locate their choices in the designated area of discussion. It shows a very easy interface, using 3D modelling. Moreover login-in is optional. It is optimal for small (plot-size) scales. The tool is open-source, developed by IAAC, where we asked information on how it could be adapted to Madrid LL case.

Activities are supported by SIN and UCD designing the whole workshop, a social expert bringing experience and sound knowledge of the Superbarrio will be contacted in order to support the event and address the process for the IT tool.

It is expected to unveil criteria and milestone to address the architects' design and obtain a space hinge that meet citizens needs.

This tool has a great potential to be integrated on host community platform and DT.

CERNA Survey

CERNA Survey: Survey planned on two rounds managed by a market research company. First round was launched in the city of Madrid, on March 2024 and second one to be launched on spring 2026. The survey is focused to investigate three main topics concerning the awareness of most effective actions to save energy, perceived norms and pluralistic ignorance. So, final analysis of the results will allow get conclusions on next actions to undertake in order to improve citizens' aptitude toward energy efficiency.

Hamilton was the company awarded for the service and budget for the subcontracting was 1.950€ without VAT. The service was developed through online interviews with a questionnaire, previously structured and programmed by SIN, with an approximate length between 10 and 15 minutes. The all process was smoothly led and it is recommendable to be replicated on other LLs.

This tool can be integrated under the DT.

We are studying the best way to disseminate CERNA results in Madrid.

3.2.3 Findings

PROBONO is uniting residents, promoting collaboration, and providing the necessary tools to empower citizens to actively participate in shaping the future of their neighbourhoods. This event serves as a model for other cities and projects to leverage citizen engagement and grassroots initiatives, fostering positive change towards a sustainable future.

According to local business leaders, citizen involvement in urban revitalisation initiatives with sustainable infrastructures is crucial and has a significant impact. Engaging citizens allows them to better understand development projects and gain deeper insight into the reasoning behind decisions, potentially reducing opposition to new solutions.

One potential next step to further contribute to the project and gather feedback from community members is to organize a follow-up workshop involving the community, developers, and energy experts. Additionally, many citizens are interested in engaging in dialogues with developers, policymakers, or energy specialists to ensure their active involvement in the design process. This workshop could utilize new innovative social engagement tools such as Geodesign to build trust between the community and developers and help ensure a successful project.

3.2.4 Adaptation and Localisation

The Madrid Nuevo Norte project aims to implement renewable energies. As a result, the workshop was specifically designed to address the management of community energy infrastructures.

Madrid LL is currently engaged in conversations about the Digital Twin integration.

Preliminary ideas are addressed to a sort of map with data points showing data coming from CERNA results, visualized through graphs and widgets. Users could interact, for example by changing the timeframe or drill down into specific metrics they are interested and get detailed

insights about specific data points, so different impacts scenario can be displayed about energy use caused by behavioural change.

3.2.5 Neighbourhood Sustainability Platform

Madrid LL is publishing findings on two main supports:

On Interacciona website to divulge the information among Acciona employees. Here news on workshop done about energy community has been already.

Figure 12: Interacciona webpage publicising the engagement workshop

On the other hand, in order to spread information to a wider public MNN web site is the community-facing platform

Figure 13: Madrid Nuevo Norte website

3.2.6 Conclusion

In summary, the activities and IT collaborative engagement tools employed in this project have successfully facilitated meaningful citizen participation in shaping sustainable community infrastructures in Madrid. By leveraging tools such as Miro Board, StoryMaps, and Survey 123, the project effectively engaged a broad spectrum of stakeholders, fostering a collaborative environment where residents, businesses, and local authorities could actively contribute to the decision-making process. The Citizen Engagement Workshop demonstrated the power of community involvement in urban revitalization, highlighting the importance of transparent communication and grassroots initiatives in driving positive change. The findings emphasize the crucial role of citizen engagement in enhancing the understanding and acceptance of sustainable infrastructure projects, potentially reducing opposition and fostering long-term success. Moving forward, the planned follow-up workshops and continued use of innovative social engagement tools, such as Geodesign, will be essential in maintaining momentum and building trust. This initiative sets a valuable precedent for the GBN.

CERNA survey has been a test of public opinion about behaviour towards energy efficiency measures. Public commitment with sustainability has arisen as a general characteristic, however misconceptions are addressing wrong behaviour in saving energy. Consequently, next step is crucial, since it aims to inform as much people as possible of wrong actions and behaviour that can be corrected and re addressed. Team is now designing side by side with City Council, the next initiative that is likely to take part in public space to approach people and quickly transfer the message through a game event.

3.3 Porto

3.3.1 Activities and IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

At Sonae Campus, two primary internal communication channels are utilized to disseminate information about Campus activities: the Sonae Campus App and internal newsletters. These channels provide coverage on a range of topics, including biodiversity, sustainability, and community initiatives.

The Sonae Campus App offers news and articles to keep employees informed about the latest projects and activities on campus. Additionally, the App includes a dedicated page where employees can share feedback and new ideas (Figure15).

Figure 14: Feedback page at Sonae Campus App

The other communication channel, the internal newsletter, is shared directly to all employees to ensure all individuals are kept informed.

These two primary internal communication channels were used to share information regarding the following activities: Vegetable Garden, House of Birds, and CERNA survey.

In addition, we used external communication channels to engage with the broader community and stakeholders outside Sonae Campus through the Social Innovation and Open Community

Lab initiative. These channels included our corporate website, social media platforms, and press releases, allowing us to share our initiatives with a wider audience.

3.3.2 Planned activities

Vegetable Garden

The vegetable garden has been part of Porto Living Lab since 2022 and serves as a hub for solidarity, team building, learning and empowerment of the communities through the donation of all vegetables. The Sonae Campus App includes a special section dedicated to our vegetable garden (Figure 16), featuring relevant information.

Figure 15: Vegetable Garden page at Sonae Campus App

House of Birds

At Sonae Campus, we have installed 25 birdhouses throughout the Campus to provide native birds with a safe environment for settling and reproducing. The main objective is to promote nidification and biodiversity among our employees (~3.500 people).

These initiatives are shared with our employees through internal communications on our Sonae Campus App, along with organizing Sonae Campus Tours focused on biodiversity and sustainability.

CERNA survey

The CERNA survey is designed to investigate three main topics: awareness of the most effective energy-saving actions, perceived norms, and pluralistic ignorance. The survey was developed as an online questionnaire, structured and programmed by SIN, and distributed in March 2024 via SONAE Campus communication channels (Figure 17).

The graphic is a vertical poster for an internal newsletter. At the top left is the 'Sonae Campus' logo in blue, followed by three overlapping circles in yellow, green, and blue. The main title in white on a dark blue background reads: 'O projeto Probono precisa da tua opinião sobre a realidade energética e climática'. Below this, a paragraph explains the project's goals, and another paragraph mentions 47 partners from 15 countries. To the right is a circular logo with 'PROBONO' and a bar chart. The next section, in blue text, states: 'O Probono levará a cabo, em diferentes países do consórcio, um questionário para analisar as perspetivas e conhecimentos do público sobre a energia e o clima.' Below this, it asks for opinions on four topics, each with an icon: energy efficiency (lightbulb), climate change (recycling symbol), carbon footprint (globe), and environmental legislation (document). A note states the survey is anonymous and confidential. At the bottom, it says 'Participa aqui.' with a brushstroke underline.

Sonae Campus

O projeto Probono precisa da tua opinião sobre a realidade energética e climática

O Probono é um projeto europeu financiado pelo Horizonte 2020 que permitirá ao Sonae Campus ser um laboratório vivo de experimentação de iniciativas de sustentabilidade, biodiversidade e energia, contribuindo para a criação de comunidades mais sustentáveis.

Este projeto envolve 47 parceiros de 15 países e em Portugal, o consórcio integra a Sonae SGPS, MC, Sierra e Capwatt.

PROBONO

O Probono levará a cabo, em diferentes países do consórcio, um questionário para analisar as perspetivas e conhecimentos do público sobre a energia e o clima.

Dá-nos a tua opinião sobre:

- Consumo de energia e eficiência energética
- Alterações climáticas
- Pegada carbónica
- Legislação ambiental

O questionário é anónimo e confidencial.

Participa aqui.

Figure 16: Internal newsletter

Social Innovation and Open Community Lab

The Social Innovation and Open Community Lab intends to be an open experimentation laboratory designed to test and evaluate innovative solutions in sustainability, with a focus on energy, biodiversity, and circularity.

This initiative aims to promote collaboration between Sonae, universities, research centres, and startups or companies, creating a dynamic environment for the development and implementation of more responsible and environmentally friendly practices. Through synergy among various partners, the Social Innovation and Open Community Lab aims to drive sustainable innovation by addressing social challenges, promoting collaborative learning, stimulating R&D activities, and contributing to the practical and experienced training of professionals committed to sustainability.

The Social Innovation and Open Community Lab initiative launched its call for applications on 20 May 2024 (Figure 18), inviting the community to explore new sustainability solutions at Sonae Campus. External communication channels (Figure 19) were used to share this initiative and engage with stakeholders outside Sonae Campus.

Figure 17: Corporate Website

Figure 18: LinkedIn

To support potential participants, an Open Day for campus visits was held on 4 June, offering an opportunity to explore the campus and its infrastructure.

3.3.3 Findings

Between April 2022 and November 2024, the vegetable garden initiative at Sonae Campus resulted in the establishment of 30 cultivation beds, the donation of 1 ton of vegetables, the conservation of 160,000 L of water, the absorption of 2 tons of CO₂, and the composting of 500 kg of organic waste. Each month, theoretical and practical training sessions are conducted in the garden, involving volunteers from Sonae Campus companies, with support from external experts from Noocity.

The CERNA survey received a total of 117 responses, and following a rigorous data cleaning process, 83 valid responses remained. Results show misconceptions about effective environmental actions and that participants support climate initiatives but believe others,

especially on a national level, are less supportive. Social norms in close personal circles were also found to strongly influence climate attitudes. Comprehensive information and detailed explanations on these results can be found in deliverable D2.6 “Social and Behavioural Implementation (I)”.

For the Social Innovation and Open Community Lab initiative, four projects were selected and announced. Meetings were scheduled with each project to evaluate their feasibility at Sonae Campus. Following these evaluations, two projects have successfully advanced and are now in active discussions for the next steps toward their implementation phase.

3.3.4 Adaptation and Localisation

The digital twin tool, being developed under WP5 in the context of Porto LL, aims to empower the Campus population to understand their energy usage and learn about sustainable practices. By providing live data on energy consumption and renewable energy production, the goal is to raise awareness and encourage more eco-conscious behaviours.

The tools will offer recommendations alongside dashboards with energy and environment impact metrics, guiding users towards small changes that collectively contribute to a greener more sustainable campus. These recommendations will help users make informed decisions about energy utilization, ultimately promoting behavioural change. The design of the dashboard and the recommendations are still being discussed and more details about it will be presented in the next WP5 deliverables.

In addition to supporting behavioural change, the DT will also contribute to the monitoring and evaluation of innovative technologies implemented in the Living Lab. By tracking key performance indicators (KPIs) such as energy efficiency, renewable energy production, and CO2 emissions reduction, the DT provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of the deployed solutions.

The future integration of the DT dashboard into SONAE Campus IT tools is under consideration. This initiative aims to enhance the visibility of results and foster collaboration, aligning with SONAE's sustainability and innovation goals.

3.3.5 Neighbourhood Sustainability Platform

Porto Living Lab team is currently assessing ideas about integrating the findings and/or IT tools into community-facing platforms.

3.3.6 Conclusion

The activities and collaborative tools effectively encouraged meaningful contributions from Campus employees, increasing engagement in PROBONO initiatives and other sustainability efforts. By utilizing Sonae's internal platforms, such as the newsletter and employee app, the project was well-communicated to both employees and stakeholders, fostering a collaborative environment where participants could actively contribute to decision-making and ongoing activity management. Sonae's website and LinkedIn were also used to engage external stakeholders in the social innovation and open community lab.

The CERNA survey gathered employee opinions on behaviour toward energy efficiency measures. Given Sonae's strong commitment to sustainability, the survey highlighted misconceptions about effective environmental actions and demonstrated that social norms in close personal circles significantly influence climate attitudes. Leveraging these internal communication channels will support targeted messaging for Porto LL employees on these topics.

Lastly, the Digital Twin tool is a valuable resource for promoting sustainability on Campus since it encourages environmentally responsible behaviour. The tool's recommendations guide users in making informed decisions that ultimately contribute to a more sustainable Campus.

3.4 Brussels

3.4.1 Activities and IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

Brussels Living Lab has developed a series of Social Innovation activities related to mobility, with most of them aiming for behaviour change, however no IT tools were adopted so far. The Living Lab is carrying out the plan for running the CERNA Survey, which, despite not being an IT tool per se, can provide very useful information to be integrated in the Digital Twin.

3.5 Aarhus

3.5.1 Activities and IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

The activity is associated with Task 2.4, which outlined the IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods that could be used for social and behavioural innovations. The aim of Task 2.4 is to adapt and deploy collaborative engagement tools and methods such as participatory mapping and storytelling, Geodesign, virtual workshops or hackathons. The IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods used for Aarhus LL are described below:

- Miro Board
- StoryMap
- Geosurvey
- Geodesign
- ProFormalise

The activity described below involves partners Aarhus University (AU), University College Dublin (UCD), and Social Innovation Norway (SIN).

3.5.2 Social engagement activities

AU Viborg Campus Transformation

In partnership with University College Dublin, Aarhus University held a Geodesign workshop on April 11, 2024, at the Research Centre Foulum, Tjele, Denmark.

The main objective of the “AU Viborg Campus Transformation Workshop” was to assess Geodesign as a concept for transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus, engaging with multiple stakeholders in a one-day workshop using maps.

3.5.2.1 Stage 1 - Preparatory Process

The preparatory process includes everything that was developed before the Geodesign Workshop. This stage consists of the following points, which are going to be described further:

- Visiting the Research Centre Foulum.
- Identifying key stakeholders through a mapping exercise based on their involvement level.

- Creating a project information landing page using ArcGIS StoryMap.
- Conducting an anonymous Geosurvey to gather information about the strengths, challenges, and opportunities at the Research Centre Foulum. This information was used for the Geodesign workshop.
- Sending out invitations to the Geodesign Workshop.

Visit the Research Centre Foulum.

A preparatory meeting was held at The Research Centre Foulum on October 25, 2023. The onsite meeting was very productive, as it significantly clarified details for UCD regarding the running and goals of the Geodesign workshop on April 11, 2024, and led to a much stronger commitment from the Research Centre Foulum stakeholders (who are not PROBONO members).

Concerning the Aarhus LL design and implementation plans, it was decided that the outcome of the workshop would be to:

- a) Result in better uptake of PROBONO technologies at the Research Centre Foulum by building owners.
- b) Identify new opportunities for other PROBONO technologies that could address the Research Centre Foulum stakeholder needs we have not yet identified.

Figure 19. Photos were taken on October 25, 2023, during the UCD site visit to the Research Centre Foulum in preparation for the Geodesign workshop on April 11, 2024.

Stakeholder Mapping

A stakeholder mapping exercise was conducted to determine the key stakeholders and their levels of involvement in the project, as engaging stakeholders is crucial to developing and testing the Geodesign tools. The exercise was created using the Miro board (see Figure 20). The groups were based on their roles in transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus.

- Stakeholders with a high level of involvement were considered for the Geodesign workshop and for sharing the anonymous survey.
- Stakeholders with a medium level of involvement were NOT considered to participate in the Geodesign workshop but were instead asked to share the anonymous Geosurvey and landing page.
- Stakeholders with a low level of involvement were NOT considered for participation in the Geodesign workshop or for sharing the anonymous Geosurvey.

The final list of stakeholders was a mix of:

- AU Viborg Teachers,
- AU Viborg Researchers,
- AU Viborg Staff Association,
- AU Viborg Current Students,
- AU Viborg partners,
- Nat-Tech Centre Representatives,
- Viborg gymnasium community,
- Viborg Municipality,
- Bolig Viborg,
- Asmildkloster Agricultural College.

The key stakeholders identified in the stakeholder mapping were emailed invitations to participate in the Geosurvey and the AU Viborg Campus Transformation Workshop.

Figure 20. Diagram of the Stakeholder Prioritisation for the AU Viborg Geodesign workshop developed on the Miro board.

StoryMap

The landing page was developed in ArcGIS StoryMap, an online storytelling platform part of ESRI, as an information portal that facilitates the project's presentation to key stakeholders (See Figure 21 and Appendix 4). The link to the StoryMap is available at the URL: <https://arcg.is/1mniqr>.

Figure 21. StoryMaps.

Geosurvey

In preparation for the Geodesign workshop, an anonymous Geosurvey was shared with the key stakeholders to gather responses from three Geosurveys: 17 about qualities, 18 about challenges, and 19 about opportunities. Figure 22 demonstrates the interface of the Geosurvey.

AU Viborg Survey - Qualities

Please tell us about a distinctive quality of the Research Centre Foulum that you value and would like to be considered in the plan for the transformation. Choose an area of the campus that possesses a quality you would like to be considered for the transformation.

Find a place for your idea

Choose a Category

Add a description

Figure 22. Geosurvey interface in which participants can read a brief description, place their idea on the map, choose a category, and add a description

The survey results were used as the foundation for the Geodesign workshop and transferred to Geodesignhub to create the initial diagrams. The Geosurvey was hosted on the landing page (StoryMaps) and shared with key stakeholders through personalised emails. Figure 23 provides an example of how the Geosurvey results, including responses for qualities, challenges, and opportunities, were presented in the Geodesign workshop.

Figure 23: Geosurvey answer.

Invitations to the Geodesign Workshop

A Geodesign Workshop was created in Eventbrite and sent to the key stakeholders. The link to the event was sent through an invitation email, which included details about the Workshop, such as time, place, and the agenda for the day (see Appendix 5). The survey was sent to approximately 650 stakeholders (with one reminder one week after launch). In total there were 196 survey responses.

3.5.2.2 Stage 2 - Geodesign Workshop

Stage 2 of the project includes everything developed during the Geodesign Workshop. This stage consists of a One-Day Geodesign Workshop.

Methodology

The one-day workshop was held on April 11th at the Research Centre Foulum in Tjele, Denmark. Geodesignhub, an online tool that facilitates co-design, discussion, and negotiation between stakeholders, was utilised during the workshop. The Geodesign workshop was divided into multiple sessions in one day, and the steps are below.

1. Review of Geosurvey Responses.
2. Creation of new diagrams
3. Negotiation between groups
4. Final design

During the workshop, participants were organised into four multi-stakeholder tables to discuss solutions for transforming the Research Centre Foulum and create a shared vision. Each table was equipped with laptops and facilitators. Participants were pre-assigned into four groups: A, B, C, and D. Each group consisted of three participants and a facilitator.

Participants

We were limited to a maximum of 35 participants due to technical and logistical challenges in managing six stakeholder groups, with five or six participants seated at each table. Engaging the stakeholders to ensure their participation in the Geosurvey and workshop was challenging, so we reduced the number of participants and representatives from each stakeholder group. One challenge was an unexpected and unavoidable clash with a competing meeting in which many key stakeholders needed to attend, who had also indicated a very strong interest in participating in the Geodesign workshop (private communication with Aarhus LL leads) after receiving the Geodesign invitation. In general, it was difficult to find a suitable date to hold the workshop that suited many key stakeholders due to the intensive renovation activity taking place on Campus Viborg. In total, we had 12 participants from the following stakeholder groups:

- AU Viborg Teachers,
- AU Viborg Researchers,
- AU Viborg Staff Association,
- AU Viborg Current Students,
- AU Viborg partners.

Workshop Development

The workshop commenced with a brief introduction to PROBONO, the project, and the activity. This was followed by two rounds of selecting projects or policies to generate a design. Subsequently, each group presented their designs to the other groups. Following the design round, there was a voting session where each group evaluated the designs of the different groups. The groups were then consolidated into two for negotiations to finalise one design and, finally, consolidated into one to discuss and finalise the activity with a single design.

Figure 24. Photographs of the presentation of the project, PROBONO and the Geosurvey insights.

Review of Geosurvey Responses

The Geosurvey provided insights used in the Geodesign Workshop to create possible projects or policies. The stories, challenges, and opportunities identified in the Geosurvey were converted into polygons on Geodesignhub. This helped to pinpoint specific locations for crucial elements of the AU Viborg Transformation vision based on input from a chosen group of stakeholders (see Figure 26). Table 5: Domains used during the Geodesign Workshop at Campus Viborg in the Aarhus LL

demonstrates the categorised domains used in the Geodesign Workshop.

Domains								
Residential	Biodiversity	Water	Recreation	Waste	Transport	Energy	Heritage	Other

Table 5: Domains used during the Geodesign Workshop at Campus Viborg in the Aarhus LL

Figure 25. Example of Geosurvey insights translated into polygons in Geodesignhub.

Participants were then tasked with choosing the projects or policies essential for transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus. Subsequently, each table's representative presented the reasons behind selecting specific projects and policies.

Creation of new diagrams

After presenting the Geosurvey results to the workshop participants (see Figure 27 and Figure 28), the first group activity began with a discussion of the strengths, challenges, and opportunities in Geodesignhub. Participants were then asked to select the most important projects or policies for transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus. Following this, a representative from each table explained the reasons behind their choices.

Figure 26. Photographs of participant presenting the projects and policies their group selected.

Figure 27. The image on the left is a photograph of participants creating new diagrams in Geodesignhub, and the figure on the right is an example of a Geosurvey response in Geodesignhub

During the first cycle, each group devised a unique strategy to transform the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus. The visual representations below (Figure 30) showcase the differences in each group's proposals, centring on various priorities. These priorities included enhancing and expanding recreational spaces for campus staff, faculty, and students, improving transportation connections with nearby towns (particularly addressing the limited and inconvenient bus routes to Viborg, Vammen, and Orum), and bolstering the campus's biodiversity by considering the potential for green areas to be developed into biodiversity tracks.

Figure 28. Version 1 (from left to right) Group A, Group B, Group C, Group D.

Negotiation between groups

In the subsequent phase, participants revised version 1 and were allowed to include additional diagrams to complement their design if necessary. The tables below compare the groups' selection and proposals on Geodesignhub.

Figure 29. (from left to right) Proposal selected by Group A and B

Figure 30. (from left to right) Proposal selected by Group C and D

Based on their design similarities, the groups voted for the group they were likely to pair with. The groups vote as shown in table 6.

++	<i>Definitely Yes</i>
+	<i>Maybe Yes</i>
-	<i>Maybe No</i>
--	<i>NEVER</i>

Table 6: Voting ranks

Consequently, the groups were matched based on analysing their priorities and similarities between their designs and the voting results. The table below illustrates the matrix of the final voting.

		A	B	C	D	Results
Evaluators	A		+	++	++	A+B
	B	-		+	+	C+D
	C	+	-		++	
	D	-	-	++		
		-1	-1	5	5	

Table 7: Matrix with the results of the voting.

Final Design

The groups A+B and C+D worked together during the negotiations to debate and discuss the proposals their groups selected to convince each other. This resulted in a negotiated strategy in which both groups agreed, representing a more refined and shared strategy.

The following maps show the shared and negotiated strategies of each combined pairing (A+B & C+D). The room was then presented with both approaches.

Figure 31. Negotiated strategy by combined groups (A+B and C+D)

After the pairing groups were presented, a negotiation debate and discussion were facilitated between them to generate one final negotiated strategy. The groups negotiated the projects and policies they considered a priority for transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus. The map below represents the final negotiated strategy. These priorities are described below:

- Residential - the restoration of existing buildings to create more co-living spaces for students and staff.
- Biodiversity - Substitute grassland with native trees and flowers, create community gardens and develop a Future Farming Educational Platform.
- Water - Create rain gardens as a natural base solution for flooding.
- Waste - Implement more compost/organic bins
- Transport—Provide more “on-campus” bikes and improve the walking and cycling infrastructure and connections with the nearby towns (particularly addressing the limited and inconvenient bus routes to Viborg, Vammen, and Orum).
- Energy - Implement more solar panels and renewable energies on campus for a net-zero campus.
- Heritage - Adaptive reuse and restoration of existing buildings for social-cultural events.
- Other - Involve students in developing the AU Viborg Campus and implement the provision of quiet rooms.

Figure 32. Final negotiated strategy by all teams

3.5.3 Findings

The valuable input received from the participants was highly appreciated, and in order to gather more insights, a feedback survey (refer to Appendix 6) was distributed to all attendees. Their responses played a crucial role in evaluating the event, and it's important to note that the survey was conducted anonymously.

Overall, the participants expressed satisfaction with the tool and acknowledged its value (refer to Tables 8 and 9 below). Nevertheless, they expressed a desire for more time for discussions and recommended involving individuals from the local government. Their input underscores the importance of their perspectives and highlights the need for their active involvement in future workshops.

Please rate the effectiveness of the workshop in enhancing your understanding of Geodesign principles for AU Viborg campus

9 responses

Table 8: Responses to the effectiveness of the workshop.

To what extent did GeodesignHub facilitate effective communication and collaboration among workshop participants during the Geodesign process for the transformation of the AU Viborg campus?

9 responses

Table 9: Responses to the effectiveness of the tool.

3.5.4 Adaptation and Localisation

The former Research Station Foulum will be transformed into the AU Viborg Campus, eventually accommodating around 800 students.

AU Viborg Campus is a green campus in Denmark that promotes the green transition in sustainable food, climate-friendly production methods, and bio-based energy solutions through education and research. Its partnership with authorities, society, and businesses enables it to turn its knowledge into practical action.

AU Viborg is part of Aarhus University and specialises in food and agriculture research, including plants, animals, food, organic farming, bioenergy, environment, climate, soil, genetics and technology. In 2023, AU Viborg opened its doors to the first students in three new degree programs

3.5.5 Neighbourhood Sustainability Platform

The suite of Geodesign tools (Miroboard, StoryMap / Landing page, and Geosurvey) are all online tools that are readily customisable to the target project. From a technological perspective this makes it highly feasible to deploy these tools within community-facing platforms, as demonstrated in the Aarhus LL. Significant input from local stakeholders is (naturally) needed to produce valid content, this can be produced by key members of local communities by following guidelines developed and demonstrated by UCD in the Aarhus LL case.

Similarly, the tools used during the Geodesign workshop are also accessible online and very feasible to be deployed in community-facing platforms.

In addition, the Aarhus LL is piloting the **ProFormalise** technologies, which are also developed by partner AU. The primary purpose of the ProFormalise suite of tools is to capture and digitalise design intentions for creating social values in buildings. For example, an architect may decide to install a spot light directed at a particular wall in order to create “curiosity” in the occupants, and thereby encourage them to explore certain areas of a building that might otherwise be unnoticed or avoided due to occupants not knowing whether they are allowed in those areas or not. Using ProFormalise technologies, such design intentions can be captured, formally represented, and “injected” into the digital model of a building (i.e. the Building Information Modelling (BIM) model). Further details of ProFormalise applied to the Aarhus LL are presented in:

- Section 4 in *D5.6 “GBN-DT Global Decision Support and Optimization Platform”* (released 05.03.2024)
- Section 3.3 in *D7.18 “Aarhus LL Design and Progress Report (I) – Initial Design and Construction Plans”* (released 08.02.2024)
- Section 3.1 and Section 5.1 in *D1.2 “GBN Analysis Tools and Decision Support System”* (released 20.06.2024)

Figure 33 illustrates a mock-up in the PROBONO platform human-machine interface (HMI) showing how users can explore as-design social values in the Aarhus LL. The mock-up showcases the idea of a heatmap indicating the regions in the Molecular Biology building in which the social values of accessibility and comfort have been explicitly designed for.

After discussions between PROBONO partners AU and UCD there may be an opportunity to exploit this technology in order to facilitate social engagement at a GBN scale, specifically:

- Enumerate, visualise and communicate social value intentions with stakeholders and community members in a visual way,
- Stimulate dialogue and negotiation amongst stakeholders about intended social values at a site.

The main obstacle is that the ProFormalise technologies have been explicitly developed for the *building* scale rather than building-complex and geographic scales, and so adopting the technology directly is not possible without further research. Nonetheless, the underlying

concepts and techniques may lead to novel approaches for GBN social engagement and thus further discussions will be undertaken between UCD, AU and SIN, perhaps in the context of the Madrid LL.

Figure 33: Mock-up of a heatmap user interface enabling stakeholders to explore as-designed social values in the Molecular Biology building in the Aarhus LL, accessed through the PROBONO platform HMI.

3.5.6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the collaborative efforts undertaken in the development and execution of the Geodesign workshop at Aarhus University's Research Centre Foulum have demonstrated the effectiveness of IT Collaborative Engagement Tools in fostering stakeholder participation and generating innovative solutions for campus transformation. Through meticulous planning, stakeholder mapping, and integrating tools such as Miro Board, StoryMap, and Geodesignhub, the workshop successfully facilitated a co-design process that aligned with the broader objectives of PROBONO.

The feedback gathered highlights the participants' appreciation for the process while also emphasising the need for extended discussions and the inclusion of local government representatives in future initiatives. The insights gained from this workshop contribute to the AU Viborg Campus's ongoing transformation and provide valuable lessons for applying similar collaborative engagement methodologies in other contexts.

3.6 Prague

3.6.1 Activities and IT Collaborative Engagement Tools

The activity is associated with Task 2.4, which outlined the IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods that could be used for social and behavioural innovations. The aim of Task 2.4 is to adapt and deploy collaborative engagement tools and methods such as participatory mapping and storytelling, Geodesign, virtual workshops or hackathons.

The IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods used for Prague LL are still to be better identified together with their Project leaders, but the scale and main characteristics of the planned technical interventions point to the potential of tools for the co-creation of solutions (e.g., Minecraft, Hackathons), prototyping and testing (e.g., Beta Project, Serious Games and Gamification) and continuing engagement through education, communication and scaling up (e.g., social networks, Change X).

3.6.2 Planned activities

User testing of the digital twin

One of the main focuses of the Prague Living Lab is Digital Twin development. Being the follower of Aarhus Living Lab, specific retrofit interventions will be determined according to the progress and development realised in Aarhus regarding the DT technology. The plan is to verify the proposed technology and planning tools through the DT and apply them later in the refurbishment of the selected building.

Our LL proposes to allocate some of the Living Labs WP2 budget to conduct professional user testing on the Digital Twin. Since this software will play a crucial role in the realization of the GBN, its usability and interface need to be tested and adjusted accordingly as part of the development process. The possible methods of testing include one-on-one interviews or focus groups with test-participants, whose feedback will be incorporated into the functionalities and design before final launch. The timeline of this activity will be determined in alignment with the stages of the development.

CERNA survey

CERNA survey is planned to be shared among the citizens of Prague. Such survey aims to investigate three main topics: awareness of the most effective energy-saving actions, perceived

social norms, and the presence of pluralistic ignorance. The final analysis will help identify actionable steps to enhance citizens' attitudes and behaviours toward energy efficiency.

Harmon research was the company awarded for the service and the budget for the service is EUR 5.350 without a WAT for 600 respondents. The whole subcontracting process is being finalized within upcoming weeks. The service will be developed through online interviews with a questionnaire, previously structured and programmed by SIN, with an approximate length between 10 and 15 minutes.

Newsletter

A yearly or biannual newsletter is under consideration to keep the audience updated on the latest news, events, and planned activities. The target audience is yet to be defined, though initial ideas include CERNA survey respondents, students, and CTU staff. Other channels already established that can be explored as options for future engagement are the Student's Union website and related social networks.

Community garden

There is a community garden at CTU with great potential to be useful for engaging people and expanding themes such as biodiversity.

3.6.3 Findings

Since most of our activities are still in the planning stage, not many suitable findings can be discussed.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable presented a range of IT tools that were adopted and tested within PROBONO's Living Labs. It also explored additional sets of IT tools that can offer relevant features in engagement activities that are still going to occur in the next phases of the project. Importantly, four tools were selected for their potential in supporting the GBN's initiatives that will engage the project stakeholders and wider populations: Placemaking Fresk, StoryMaps, CartoSpot and CERNA Survey.

A relevant finding is that when adopted, either in online formats or in combination with analogue tools and approaches, IT tools can facilitate social inclusion and accessibility, collection of participant's inputs and co-creation of outputs. A clear example of this was observed in the Geodesign Workshops performed in Dublin and Aarhus, where this particular tool was tested with relevant success and very positive feedback from participants.

For their technological nature, IT tools can evolve, change or become obsolete. This makes it even more important that the process of choice for a tool or a combination of tools needs to have an objective vision of what is needed, so the best tools can be identified. IT tools are not a silver bullet but can offer many benefits for facilitating engagement and collaboration, such as accessibility, interaction and visualisation of different scenarios. If adopted with clear objectives that aim to involve users and communities in inclusive and just ways, they are powerful resources for supporting meaningful and memorable activities.

Finally, the IT tools give the Living Labs the advantage of having digital resources that can be considered for integration in PROBONO's Digital Twin, leaving a legacy for their respective GBNs and beyond.

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Appendix 1: List of IT Tools by needs and approaches (detailed)

Need	Approach	IT Collaborative Engagement Tools	Further explanation
Co-production of knowledge and collective understanding	Participatory mapping and storytelling	Geosurvey	A geosurvey is a versatile tool designed to collect data quickly and efficiently. Its purpose is to identify and map existing sites and buildings in a given area. The geosurvey gathers initial information about the values, ideas, challenges and opportunities of the place. It plays a crucial role in participatory mapping and storytelling by facilitating community engagement, collecting spatial data, providing visualization tools, supporting collaborative mapping, and offering accessibility and flexibility. These features empower storytellers to create compelling narratives that reflect the voices, experiences, and spatial realities of the communities they represent.
		Survey 123	Survey123 is a tool that allows for participatory mapping. It is very user-friendly, with customizable forms that can be used on mobile devices. With this tool, users can collect data in real-time and engage the community to contribute valuable insights to decision-making processes. By integrating with the ArcGIS platform, Survey123 empowers users to unlock the potential of advanced GIS tools and transform data into insights that inspire and drive progress. This tool is an excellent way for communities to actively participate in the mapping process and make a difference.
		Open Street Maps*	OpenStreetMap is a platform that offers global map data in a unified tagging system. The data is accessible for every country in the world, and in many areas, the quality of the data is excellent. You can also contribute to improving the quality of the data since the platform is open. OpenStreetMap is an essential tool for participatory mapping and storytelling. It democratizes access to geographical data, encourages community involvement, allows customization, supports various visualization formats, and promotes the principles of open data.
		Maptionnaire*	Maptionnaire is a platform for collaborating and gathering data within communities. It offers customizable surveys, geospatial analysis, and remote participation features. Storytellers can use these tools to engage their audience, gather relevant data, and create compelling narratives.

Need	Approach	IT Collaborative Engagement Tools	Further explanation
		CartoSpot	The map-based participation engagement platform that enables anyone to enhance collaboration and dialogue among people, groups or entire communities. Collect ground-level data, local knowledge and insights for managing and building better spaces and more inclusive and livable places.
	Storytelling	Story Maps	ArcGIS StoryMap is an online storytelling platform part of ESRI that facilitates the design process. An innovative approach to present the projects/workshop to the community. It can be convine with other ESRI tools such as Experiencebuilder and dashboard
Tools for engagement and decision making	Co-creation processes	Geodesign*	Geodesign is a collection of principles and techniques that aim to involve all stakeholders and professionals in the collaborative design of the best possible solution for spatial challenges in both built and natural environments. This is achieved by integrating all available data and techniques into a single, cohesive process. Geodesign integrates GIS technology, design thinking, and participatory approaches to engage stakeholders in co-creating sustainable solutions. This process enables data-informed decision-making, scenario planning and evaluation, iterative design, and collaborative decision-support, resulting in positive outcomes for communities and environments.
		Minecraft*	Minecraft, an open-world cross-platform game, offers a virtual environment composed of blocks, with each block representing a volume of 1 m ³ in the real world. Minecraft is a sandbox game, which means it lacks a predefined goal, allowing players the freedom to determine their objectives and learn how to interact with the virtual world. Minecraft enables stakeholders to collaborate, prototype, engage communities, educate, and visualize spatial data. By leveraging its potential, stakeholders can foster inclusive approaches to planning, design, and decision-making that empower communities and create positive outcomes for the built environment.
		Hackathons	Hackathons promote co-creation through collaborative problem-solving, rapid prototyping, idea sharing, community engagement, and prototype validation. They enable stakeholders to create innovative solutions, addressing complex challenges and generating positive impact in diverse domains.

Need	Approach	IT Collaborative Engagement Tools	Further explanation
	Online voting	Helios Voting*	Helios Voting is an open-source, web-based electronic voting system. Users can vote in elections and users can create elections. Anyone can cast a ballot; however, for the final vote to be counted, the voter's identification must be verified. Helios uses homomorphic encryption to ensure ballot secrecy. Helios Voting is a secure and customizable platform for online voting that enhances engagement and promotes inclusivity, transparency, and trust in governance.
		Agora voting / nVotes*	Agora is a simple and secure online voting system that works on all digital devices. It uses blockchain technology and provides a transparent and inclusive platform for people to democratically participate in decision-making processes. Agora Voting helps promote trust, inclusivity, and transparency in the governance of organizations, communities, and institutions.
		eBallot*	eBallot is an online voting software and services provider that specializes in secure, closed voting events. eBallot voting is a user-friendly, accessible, and secure platform for conducting online voting. It empowers stakeholders to participate in democratic decision-making processes, fostering inclusivity, transparency, and trust in governance.
	Online workshops	Miro Board	Miro is an online whiteboard that enables collaboration among multiple individuals. It facilitates interaction among people irrespective of their physical location. Miro enables real-time updates and contributions, making it an excellent tool for virtual workshops where participants may be geographically dispersed.
		Etherpad	Etherpad is an online workshop tool that enables real-time document editing, version control, rich text formatting, and integration with other tools. It facilitates productive and inclusive workshops by empowering participants to collaborate and contribute to decision-making processes, leading to meaningful outcomes and actions.
		Mural	Mural is a digital space that enhances collaboration. With visual aids and engaging features, it facilitates remote collaboration, workshops, ideation, and decision-making. Mural empowers teams to work together effectively, driving meaningful outcomes and actions in diverse contexts.

Need	Approach	IT Collaborative Engagement Tools	Further explanation
Testing	Serious games and gamification	Minecraft*	Minecraft, an open-world cross-platform game, offers a virtual environment composed of blocks, with each block representing a volume of 1 m ³ in the real world. Minecraft is a sandbox game, which means it lacks a predefined goal, allowing players the freedom to determine their objectives and learn how to interact with the virtual world. Minecraft promotes experiential learning, problem-solving, collaboration, creativity, and personalized learning. By using the power of play, Minecraft offers meaningful learning experiences that develop essential skills for success in the digital age.
		Urban Nature Explorer*	The Urban Nature Explorer is a tool that aims to promote the development and visualization of nature-based solutions for various urban sustainability challenges. These challenges may include climate change, stormwater management, or social cohesion. The tool assesses the costs, benefits, and impacts of various alternative solutions to help users make informed decisions. Urban Nature Explorer is a serious game that promotes awareness, appreciation, and conservation of urban biodiversity. It combines education, exploration, gamified challenges, community engagement, and citizen science to transform urban exploration into an immersive and interactive gaming experience.
		SuperBarrio*	It is a video game tool/platform for the participatory design of public space. Superbarrio uses gamification strategies, expanding the potential audience of existing participatory design processes, and increasing good relationships between citizens and neighborhood. SuperBarrio is a serious game that empowers and engages communities to promote social activism. It combines education, gamified challenges, and real-world impact to inspire players to become superheroes for social justice.
		NegoDesign	The NegoDesign tool is a digital open-source negotiation tool based on Geodesign and Serious Gaming. It engages communities and local authorities in co-creating design solutions for spatial decision-making with conflicting perspectives. Currently deployed in three pilot sites: Eleusina, Milan, and Ballina.
	Prototyping	Beta Projects*	Beta Projects are cost-effective trials that might help us address and understand key issues in our community before possible wider implementation
Facilitating continuing engagement	Education and	Newsletters*	A newsletter is a periodically-sent email that informs your audience of the latest news, tips, or updates relating to your products or services.

Need	Approach	IT Collaborative Engagement Tools	Further explanation
	communication	Social Networks*	Social networks are vital for education and communication. They allow us to share educational content, communicate, and collaborate effectively over time. By leveraging social networking's power, educators, learners, and professionals can connect and support learning, professional development, and knowledge sharing in diverse contexts.
	Scaling up	Waypoint*	Waypoint is a scalable tool that facilitates continued engagement. It provides centralized coordination, communication, community engagement, resource sharing, and analytics capabilities. By leveraging its power, organizations can scale up their initiatives, projects, or campaigns to reach a larger audience across geographical boundaries over time.
		Change X*	Chanfe X connects communities to proven ideas and funding by empowering local changemakers with proven ideas from social innovators and accessible funding from our partners. It's aim is to build healthier, more inclusive and sustainable communities.
Integration of engagement tools	Suites	Consul*	Consul is a digital platform that is open source and designed to promote participatory democracy and enhance citizen engagement at the local level. It is an integration of engagement tools that allows for comprehensive management and conduction of various forms of participatory processes, such as consultations, deliberations, and collaborative decision-making.
		Decidim*	Decidim is an open-source digital platform that aims to facilitate participatory democracy and increase citizen engagement at the local level. It integrates various engagement tools and provides a comprehensive suite of features for managing and conducting different forms of participatory processes. These include consultations, deliberations, and collaborative decision-making.
		Delib Citizen Space	Delib Citizen Space is a user-friendly platform that enables effective public engagement. It provides organizations with the tools to manage consultations, gather feedback, and make informed decisions that align with the views of their communities. With this platform, stakeholders can easily collect valuable insights that help drive positive change and improve relationships with their constituents.

Appendix 2: Dublin LL - 2024 Geodesign Workshop

Introduction

PROBONO is a research project funded by the European Union (EU) dedicated to establishing guidelines for developing Green Building Neighbourhoods to ensure a sustainable future.

This report is a component of Work Package 2, focusing on employing a variety of participatory, co-design methods to foster stakeholder (including citizen) involvement. It is associated with Task 2.4, overseen by UCD, and seeks to customise and implement collaborative engagement tools and methods, including participatory mapping, Geodesign, virtual workshops, and hackathons.

The report is associated with Task 2.4, which outlined the IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods that could be used for the social and behavioural innovations performed in each of the Living Labs. The aim of Task 2.4 is to adapt and deploy collaborative engagement tools and methods such as participatory mapping and storytelling, Geodesign, virtual workshops or hackathons. The social and behavioural innovations were defined in D2.5. The IT Collaborative Engagement Tools and methods used for the task reported in this report are described below:

- **Geosurvey:** This participatory mapping tool was chosen to facilitate community engagement by collecting spatial data and providing visualisation tools.
- **ArcGIS StoryMap:** Selected as the storytelling tool, this online platform by ESRI aids in the design process through compelling storytelling.
- **Geodesign:** A participatory design method incorporating stakeholder input, geospatial modelling, impact simulations, and real-time feedback to support planning and decision-making (McElvaney, Shannon, and Doug Walker, 2013).
- **GeodesignHub:** Geodesignhub is a collaborative platform designed to facilitate decision-making in complex spatial planning and design projects. It was used as a tool enables participants to engage in map-based negotiations, fostering consensus on development strategies (Ref: GeodesigHub).

1.1 Common Ground: Campus, Climate and Community

The Common Ground workshop, hosted by University College Dublin (UCD) on October 19, 2024, was a pivotal event within the broader framework of the EU-funded PROBONO project, which aims to create Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs) as models of sustainable urban development across Europe. The workshop's primary objective was to evaluate and demonstrate the potential of Geodesign as a tool for multi-stakeholder engagement, particularly in transforming UCD's campus environment to foster stronger connections with its surrounding

communities. With a vision set for 2050, this event engaged a diverse group of participants—including UCD researchers, architecture students, local community members, and city officials—in a day-long collaborative session focused on developing proposals for enhancing campus accessibility and interaction with adjacent neighbourhoods.

Throughout the workshop, participants employed Geodesign tools and methods to analyse six key sites around the UCD campus. This process facilitated discussions that reflected the unique needs, aspirations, and perspectives of the different stakeholders involved.

By collaborating in this way, the workshop sought to address several specific objectives:

- (1) To create a platform for students and community members to exchange ideas, co-design solutions, and explore transformative design projects;
- (2) To activate underutilized campus spaces, envisioning them as hubs for interaction, creativity, and community engagement; and
- (3) To establish a resilient network of individuals and groups committed to advancing sustainability and climate resilience across campus and local communities.

1.2 Work Progress

The preparatory process encompassed all activities developed in advance of the Geodesign Workshop. This stage included several key elements:

1. Stage 1

1. **Preliminary Lectures:** As part of the 2nd-year design studio, students attended preliminary lectures on UCD's history to build a foundational understanding of the campus and its surrounding context. Before these lectures, surveys were distributed to local residents to gather insights, understand community interests, and assess potential engagement in future initiatives. All student sessions were open to the community, fostering a sense of inclusion and shared purpose within UCD.

Students were also introduced to the objectives of the Geodesign Workshop and hosted architectural studios that practiced co-design principles, preparing them for collaborative roles in the workshop.

- b. **Site Analysis:** Students began analysing specific campus-edge sites, focusing on spatial and social dynamics as a foundation for the workshop's design discussions.

2. Stage 2

1. **Participatory Survey (Mitheal):** A survey, designed for the UCD campus community, was developed to gather insights into the stories, values, challenges, and opportunities associated with Belfield Campus.

2. **Strategy Development:** MSc Architecture, Urbanism & Climate Action students commenced work on developing strategic proposals tailored to each site, contributing to the overarching vision for campus-community integration.
3. **Stage 3**
Geodesign Workshop: An immersive and collaborative event where community members, students, and local leaders came together to reimagine UCD's campus edges through a lens of sustainability and climate resilience.
4. **Stage 4**
- a. **Feedback Survey:** A brief survey was distributed to all participants, inviting them to share their thoughts and insights on the workshop experience.
- b. **Presentation for 2nd-Year Students:** MSc students are expected to present the results for 2nd year students to enhance their design
- c. **Common Ground Exhibition: Connecting Campus, Community, and Climate:** Participants are invited to attend an exhibition showcasing the creative solutions developed by our students. This exhibition celebrates the collaboration between campus and community, highlighting climate-resilient ideas shaped by the perspectives shared during the workshop.

Figure 1. Timeline diagram of the 3 stages of the Geodesign Workshop.

2. Stage 1 - Preparatory Process

2.1 Preliminary Lectures & Community Survey

To support a meaningful understanding of UCD Belfield campus and to lay a foundation for the Geodesign workshop, it was essential for students to gain a thorough grasp of the campus's historical, cultural, and spatial context. Foundational lectures introduced students to UCD's evolving landscape and heritage values. These sessions, open to the community to strengthen relationships with neighboring communities, aimed to deepen students' awareness of the unique characteristics and complexities of UCD's campus edges.

Additionally, a workshop on systems thinking and territorial design equipped students with tools to analyze and synthesize diverse environmental and social information. Three architects presented how collaborative work has shaped their practices, each bringing a unique perspective that enriched the discussion. These presentations broadened and deepened students' understanding of "community," offering a more invigorating perspective on the role of collaboration in both architectural practice and community engagement. This preparation enabled students to approach the site with a well-rounded perspective, enriching their design responses and fostering informed engagement with the campus.

2.2 Site analysis

Each group of 2nd-year students produced a Storymap to represent the data they gathered and their understanding of the area. These Storymaps were prepared to be shared with the UCD community. Each group was assigned to one of six sites and focused on conveying what they learned during the first stage for their specific location. Information on site heritage and background, site surveys, tree mapping, and walkthroughs was also included. These Storymaps provided a valuable foundation for the MSc students, allowing them to gain a deeper understanding of the sites and to begin developing their own strategies.

3. Stage 2 - Data Collection

3.1 Participatory Survey

In anticipation of the Geodesign workshop, an anonymous survey was conducted among key UCD Belfield staff and members of neighbouring communities to gather feedback across three essential areas: values, challenges, and opportunities related to the Belfield Campus. This survey aimed to capture community insights by inviting participants to share the places, memories, and activities that foster their connection to the campus.

The responses provided valuable perspectives on what makes Belfield significant to its community. This understanding has been instrumental in shaping strategies to strengthen the campus's relationship with its surrounding areas. Through this map, which reflects UCD's stories and values, we aim to present a narrative of community connection.

The interface of Mitheal UCD Belfield Particimap

3.2 Strategies Development

The stories, challenges, and opportunities identified in the Geosurvey were transformed into spatial representations using the Geodesignhub tool, where they were mapped as polygons. This process enabled the identification of specific locations for UCD's campus vision, grounded in community input.

Table 1 illustrates the categorised domains applied in the Geodesign Workshop, where MSc Architecture, Urbanism & Climate Action students developed strategic, site-specific proposals. These strategies, rooted in a comprehensive analysis of public feedback, transformed shared memories, challenges, and opportunities into actionable interventions. The Geosurvey insights informed the Geodesign Workshop, facilitating the creation of potential projects and policies that reflect and support campus-community integration.

This collaborative approach not only created a unified vision for the campus but also underscored the value of community input in shaping meaningful, sustainable interventions.

A key part of the strategy development involved creating suitability maps, designed to identify optimal locations for proposed interventions. These maps, based on the students' site analysis, were instrumental in refining strategic proposals, ensuring that interventions were thoughtfully situated within the campus context. This approach not only provided a structured framework for the strategies but also demonstrated a practical application of geodesign principles in enhancing campus-community connections.

Agreed Strategies for Campus-Community Integration

Based on community insights and site analysis, the following strategic themes were developed to guide interventions aimed at enhancing UCD Belfield’s connection with its surrounding communities:

1. **Connectivity** – Strengthening physical and social links between the campus and neighbouring areas to foster inclusivity and access.
2. **Heritage** – Preserving and celebrating the cultural and historical assets of the campus, reinforcing a sense of place and continuity.
3. **Green and Blue Infrastructure** – Expanding green spaces and integrating water management systems to support biodiversity, improve environmental resilience, and enhance aesthetic value.
4. **Mobility** – Enhancing transportation options to ensure safe, efficient movement within and beyond the campus.
5. **Active Mobility** – Promoting walking, cycling, and other forms of sustainable, health-focused transport to improve accessibility and reduce reliance on cars.
6. **Housing** – Addressing student and staff accommodation needs to foster a more inclusive and balanced campus community.
7. **Retail** – Developing campus retail offerings that align with community needs, enhancing the convenience and vibrancy of campus life.
8. **Amenity and Public Services** – Enhancing campus amenities and expanding public services to foster community engagement and ensure accessible resources for everyone.

The visual representations below illustrate the diverse strategies and site-specific priorities identified by each group, showcasing their unique approaches to creating a connected, sustainable, and vibrant UCD Belfield Campus for the future.

<i>Domains</i>							
<i>Connectivity</i>	<i>Heritage</i>	<i>G&B Infrastructure</i>	<i>Mobility</i>	<i>Active Mobility</i>	<i>Housing</i>	<i>Amenity</i>	<i>Retail</i>

Table 1. Domains used during the Geodesign Workshop.

Figure 2. Example of Geosurvey insights translated into polygons in Geodesignhub.

3. Stage 3: Geodesign Workshop

At the start of the Geodesign workshop, participants were introduced to the workshop's purpose and the concept behind it. A brief overview of the workshop objectives was also provided.

Participants were then divided into six tables, with each table focusing on one site. Each table included two facilitators (students in this case), one community member, and additional participants, some of whom had a background with UCD or were involved in its activities.

Discussions began with each group presenting a brief overview of their strategies, covering the core ideas behind the tool and explaining what the polygons represented. This initial exchange helped participants align on the tool's purpose and gain a spatial understanding of each group's strategy.

Round 1 of discussions then commenced, where groups engaged in negotiations and initial vision development. Each group voted on the strategies they felt best aligned with their goals and addressed observed issues within UCD. While focusing on their assigned sites, they also considered the broader campus context to establish a foundation for discussion. This stage

encouraged open dialogue about the strengths, challenges, and opportunities presented by the Geodesignhub tool in envisioning UCD Belfield’s integration with surrounding communities.

In **Round 2**, groups advanced to developing distinct strategies for reimagining the UCD Belfield Campus. Each table prioritized site-specific elements based on the unique characteristics of their location—some sites, for instance, highlighted historical assets, while others focused on natural features. Afterwards, each table selected a spokesperson to share their group’s chosen priorities and reasoning. At this stage, participants began sketching their ideas with facilitator guidance, combining the Geodesignhub polygons with their own drawings to capture a fuller vision (Figure 8).

Building negotiations

In the next phase, groups entered a negotiation process, revisiting and refining their initial strategies (Version 1). During this collaborative step, participants were encouraged to make adjustments to their proposals and, if necessary, add complementary diagrams to strengthen and clarify their design intentions.

The tables below provide a comparative overview of each group’s selections and proposals, as represented on Geodesignhub. This comparison highlights the evolving priorities, adjustments, and shared visions that emerged through the negotiation process, reflecting a collective effort to achieve a cohesive and impactful strategy for UCD Belfield Campus.

Based on their design similarities, the groups voted for the group they were likely to pair with. The groups vote as shown in the table below:

++	Definitely Yes
+	Maybe Yes
-	Maybe No
--	NEVER

Table 2. Voting ranks.

Consequently, the groups were matched based on showing their interest in the other groups that presented. Groups voted for each other based on their interest and similarities while they presented their visions in round 2.

	N11	NEW	NOVA	ROE	ROSE	WOOD
N11		++	+	+	-	++
NEW	-		+	+	++	+
NOVA	-	+		-	-	++
ROE	-	++	++		-	+
ROSE	-	+	++	+		++
WOOD	+	-	++	-	++	

Table 3. Matrix with the results of the voting.

Final Design

Throughout the negotiations, groups A and B, as well as groups C and D, collaborated to debate and discuss their respective proposals. This collective effort led to the development of a refined and mutually agreed-upon strategy. The resulting negotiated strategy was then presented to the room, incorporating input from both combined pairings (A+B and C+D) as illustrated in Figure 16.

Stage 4 - Geodesign Workshop Feedback

The input received from the participants was greatly appreciated. To gather further insights, a feedback survey was distributed to all attendees.

Overall, the participants expressed satisfaction with the tool and acknowledged its value. However, they expressed a desire for more time for discussions and recommended involving individuals from the local government. Their input underscores the importance of their perspectives and highlights the need for their active involvement in future workshops.

Appendix 3 – Madrid LL - Community infrastructure for energy community for a GBN Storymap

This section presents the StoryMap elaborated in preparation of the engagement workshop in Madrid and how related aspects to a GBN were addressed. Link to the StoryMap here:

<https://arcg.is/1W4zHe>

¡Nos interesa saber tu opinión!

Te invitamos a participar en nuestra encuesta acerca de Infraestructuras Comunitarias, que la encontraras al final.

Haz clic [aquí](#)

PROBONO

Un **barrio sostenible** necesita **infraestructuras sostenibles**. El empoderamiento ciudadano en la gestión de estas infraestructuras es clave.

Por ello, en el contexto del proyecto de investigación **H2020 PROBONO** queremos analizar cuáles de estas infraestructuras son las más prioritarias y cuáles son los retos para una correcta gestión.

Objetivo

Priorizar el bienestar tanto de las personas como del medio ambiente frente a la creciente urbanización y los avances tecnológicos, logrando así **Barrios Sostenibles y comunidades prósperas** manteniendo un **equilibrio** armonioso entre la **naturaleza y ciudadanía** para el beneficio mutuo y el futuro.

¿Cómo se va a lograr?

Mediante la **implementación de infraestructuras urbanas eficientes y sostenibles, empleando tecnologías y enfoques innovadores** para lograr la **transición a energía limpia**.

Para saber más acerca del proyecto H2020 PROBONO haz clic en el siguiente enlace.

Barrios Sostenibles | PROBONO

Visión y objetivos del proyecto PROBONO para la construcción de barrios sostenibles

<https://www.probonoh2020.eu>

Living Labs

Los **Living Labs de PROBONO** son **ecosistemas de innovación abierta, iterativos y de gran escala**, que operan en un contexto territorial, integrando procesos concurrentes de investigación e innovación dentro de una asociación público-privada.

Madrid Living Lab

Madrid Living Lab se localiza en **Madrid Nuevo Norte** concretamente en el ámbito de Las Tablas Oeste. La infraestructura propuesta consiste en el desarrollo de una **red de distrito de frío y calor** que use la **energía geotérmica** para **resolver las necesidades térmicas** de los nuevos edificios a construir en esta zona de Madrid Nuevo Norte a través de un modelo de gobernanza como son las **Comunidades Energéticas Renovables**.

Diagrama de Red de distrito Frío y calor usando energía geotérmica

Madrid Nuevo Norte

Madrid Nuevo Norte es el **gran proyecto del Madrid del siglo XXI**. El proyecto surge de la necesidad de **integrar la estación de Chamartín y sus instalaciones ferroviarias en la ciudad**, ya que durante más de 50 años estas infraestructuras han dividido el norte de Madrid y causando problemas a los ciudadanos, así como crear una ciudad **100% sostenible**.

Madrid Nuevo Norte se enfoca en crear un **entorno agradable y saludable** al fomentar el disfrute de las calles y espacios públicos, al mismo tiempo que **busca reducir el impacto ambiental**.

El proyecto se estructurará en **cuatro zonas**:

1. Estación de Chamartín
2. Distrito Empresarial de Chamartín
3. Malmea-San Roque-Tres Olivos
4. Las Tablas.

Estas cuatro áreas tienen independencia en su desarrollo.

El siguiente mapa es un mapa interactivo de la ciudad de Madrid, en donde se muestra el proyecto Madrid Nuevo Norte conectando los vecindarios aledaños.

Infraestructura Comunitaria Sostenible

Cumpliendo con el **objetivo del proyecto PROBONO**, se propone desarrollar **Infraestructura comunitaria de generación de energía térmica**.

INFRAESTRUCTURA DE RECARGA DE VEHÍCULOS
ELÉCTRICOS Y ALMACENAMIENTO

INFRAESTRUCTURA DE GENERACIÓN DE ENERGÍA TÉRMICA

¡ Nos interesa saber tu opinión !

Te pedimos tu colaboración en contestar una **breve encuesta** para saber tu opinión acerca de **las infraestructuras comunitarias** y **¿Cuáles son más importantes para el desarrollo de un barrio sostenible?**

Haz clic [aquí](#)

Colaboradores

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Agradecimientos a nuestros colaboradores, Acciona y Smart Innovation Norway
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Especial agradecimiento al Ayuntamiento de Madrid y Crea Madrid Nuevo Norte

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Appendix 4 – Madrid LL - Community infrastructure for energy community for a Green Building Neighbourhood Survey

This section presents the interface of the Survey used in Madrid LL, where respondents provided relevant information that was used in preparation of the workshop.

Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Queremos Conocerte

¿A cuál de estos grupos perteneces?*

 Residente Trabajador Dueño de un negocio Otro

¿Cuál es tu identidad de género?*

 Masculino Femenino Prefiero no decir Otro

Selecciona tu rango de edad*

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Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Queremos saber qué tanto conoces sobre las infraestructuras comunitarias sostenibles

Infraestructura de generación de energía renovable

Infraestructura de generación de energía renovable

Las **energías renovables** son un tipo de **energías derivadas de fuentes naturales** que llegan a reponerse más rápido de lo que pueden consumirse. **Un ejemplo** de estas fuentes son la **energía fotovoltaica** o la **eólica**.

La aparición de estas tecnologías permiten que la **energía pueda generarse en el mismo sitio donde se consumen**, mejorando la **eficiencia energética** y **reduciendo las pérdidas** por distribución, pero requiriendo de una inversión y una gestión por parte de los propietarios.

¿Qué crees que son las comunidades energéticas renovables?*

Elige la opción que consideras correcta

- Asociaciones de empresas para generar, gestionar y vender energía
- Asociaciones comunitarias que se unen para generar, gestionar y compartir los beneficios de la energía renovable en sus barrios
- Empresas que dan servicios de mejora en la eficiencia energética de los edificios

¿Qué tan interesado está por las energías renovables?*

¿Qué tan de acuerdo estás con la implementación de energías renovables en tu barrio?*

¿Estás de acuerdo con la instalación de paneles solares en tu edificio?*

- Sí
- No
- No estoy seguro

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Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Queremos saber qué tanto conoces sobre las infraestructuras comunitarias sostenibles

Infraestructura Verde

La **infraestructura verde** es una red de **espacios naturales** que **mejora la resiliencia** ante impactos como el **cambio climático**, conservando la biodiversidad del lugar.

¿Qué preferirías tener en tu cubierta (azotea)?*

Zona verde estancial comunitaria

Huerto urbano productivo de autogestión

Prefiero que mi cubierta no tenga zonas verdes

¿Dónde te gustaría que estuviesen localizados los huertos urbanos?*

Parques y jardines

Parcelas en desuso de forma temporal

En áreas comunes dentro de los edificios

¿Para ti, es importante la instalación de fachadas verdes en los edificios?
*

Muy importante Importante No lo tengo claro Poco importante Nada importante

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Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Queremos saber qué tanto conoces sobre las infraestructuras comunitarias sostenibles

Infraestructura de
recarga de vehículos
eléctricos y almacenamiento

Los **vehículos eléctricos** necesitan el desarrollo de una **red de puntos o estaciones que permita la recarga** de estos vehículos.

Estos puntos o estaciones pueden desarrollarse en varias **localizaciones**:

1. En las plazas de aparcamiento privadas de cada edificio.
2. En gasolineras dónde el usuario vaya a recargar con estaciones de carga ultra-rápida su vehículo.
3. En los aparcamientos de las vías públicas, instalando en el espacio público los equipos necesarios para permitir esta recarga.
4. En aparcamientos de acceso público tales como los parkings públicos o privados.

Además, las **baterías de los vehículos** ofrecen la posibilidad de utilizar estas mismas para balancear la demanda de la red. Es decir, cuando el vehículo se encuentre **cargando en localizaciones de carga lenta** tales como los **edificios privados**, se puede **usar la batería** del vehículo eléctrico **para entregar energía a la red eléctrica** cuando haya un pico de demanda y se pueda cargar el vehículo cuando la demanda es baja. De esta manera, se podría **vender electricidad a la red** cuando tenga un precio elevado y comprar electricidad cuando el precio sea bajo, asegurando que el vehículo estará completamente cargado cuando se necesite.

¿Tienes coche eléctrico?*

Sí

No

¿Dónde crees que deberían estar las estaciones de recarga de coches eléctricos?*

En puntos de recarga dedicados como las gasolineras

En los aparcamientos en las calles

En los aparcamientos privados dentro de los edificios

En los aparcamientos de acceso público

¿Si tuvieses coche eléctrico, estarías dispuesto a vender la energía almacenada en la batería cuándo no lo estés usando, aunque reduzca la vida útil de tu batería?*

Sí

No

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Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Queremos saber qué tanto conoces sobre las infraestructuras comunitarias sostenibles

Infraestructura de generación de energía térmica

Los edificios demandan energía.

Por un lado, se demanda la energía para la **iluminación, ventilación o el uso general de electricidad** de las viviendas: electrodomésticos, mobiliario, etc.

Por otro lado, los edificios **también demandan frío y calor**. **Frío** durante los meses de **verano** y **calor** durante **todo el año** para poder calentar el agua de nuestras duchas o las calefacciones durante el invierno.

En España esta transformación de la energía en frío y calor se ha hecho con

calderas o bombas de calor (aire acondicionado, aerotermia, geotermia) individuales **para cada vivienda o comercio**. Es decir, cada propietario "**compra**" electricidad, gas u otro **combustible** para transformarlo en calor o frío.

Sin embargo, existen otros modelos que plantean mayores eficiencias. De forma simplificada se podrían resumir **3 modelos para la generación de ese frío y calor**:

- **Generación en cada vivienda** con propiedad y gestión privada
- **Generación centralizada** por edificio. Este sistema es más eficiente, pero requiere una gestión comunitaria por parte de la Comunidad de Vecinos
- **Generación a nivel distrito**. El cual es el sistema que normalmente suele ser más eficiente.

El sistema de **generación a nivel distrito plantea 2 alternativas** principales de propiedad y gestión

- **La instalación es propiedad de una empresa privada o pública** que factura a los usuarios finales por el frío y calor que les entrega. Igual que se factura por la electricidad, el gas o el agua, se factura por el frío o el calor.
- **La instalación es propiedad de los vecinos** que están conectados a la red y a través de un contrato de gestión, la gestionan a nivel supracomunidad de vecinos.

¿Con cuál de estas opciones estás de acuerdo?*

Prefiero instalaciones individuales

Prefiero aprovechar la eficiencia de una instalación centralizada en mi edificio y compartir la gestión con la comunidad de vecinos

Prefiero que directamente una empresa privada me de el servicio y no tener responsabilidad de gestión

Prefiero ser lo más eficiente energéticamente e involucrarme en la generación de frío y calor en mi barrio

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Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Prioridades y preocupaciones

¿Cuál es la infraestructura comunitaria sostenible que crees más beneficiosa para tu barrio?*

Ordena las siguientes opciones en función a tu prioridad

Infraestructuras de recarga del vehículo eléctrico y almacenamiento

Infraestructuras de generación de energía térmica

Infraestructuras de generación de energía renovable

Infraestructura verde

Reset

¿Cuál es la infraestructura comunitaria sostenible que crees más beneficiosa para tu edificio?*

Ordena las siguientes opciones en función a tu prioridad

Infraestructura verde

Infraestructuras de generación de energía renovable

Infraestructuras de generación de energía térmica

Infraestructuras de recarga del vehículo eléctrico y almacenamiento

Reset

¿Valoraría que un barrio tuviera infraestructura comunitaria sostenible a la hora de adquirir una vivienda?*

Si

No

¿Cuál de estas infraestructuras comunitarias sostenibles considerarías más importante para la adquisición de tu vivienda?*

Ordena las siguientes opciones en función a tu prioridad

Infraestructuras de generación de energía térmica

Infraestructura verde

Infraestructuras de generación de energía renovable

Infraestructuras de recarga del vehículo eléctrico y almacenamiento

Reset

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Infraestructuras Comunitarias para una Comunidad Energética ...

Te invitamos a participar

Si estás interesado en participar en futuras actividades relacionadas a las Comunidades energéticas sostenibles, déjanos tu correo electrónico:

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Enviar

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Appendix 5 – Madrid LL - Miro board of the SWOT analysis

INFRAESTRUCTURA VERDE

<p>INTRODUCCIÓN</p> <p>Objetivo: Generar un marco técnico dentro del cual se identificarán Fortalezas, Debilidades, Oportunidades y Amenazas a nivel local y global.</p> <p>Resultado: Identificación de los factores claves positivos y negativos que influyen en el futuro desarrollo del proyecto, así como también sus oportunidades y limitaciones.</p>	<p>Fortalezas</p> <p>Elementos internos basados en los aspectos o beneficios de los recursos existentes</p>	<p>Debilidades</p> <p>Áreas internas o sustantivos que necesitan mejorarse</p>
<p>INSTRUCCIONES</p> <p>Paso 01: Seleccione un tipo de gestión por equipo</p> <p>Step 02: Toma una nota adhesiva y colócala debajo de las fortalezas, debilidades, oportunidades o amenazas.</p>		
<p>DEFINICIÓN</p> <p>La infraestructura verde es una red de espacios naturales que mejora la resiliencia ante impactos como el cambio climático, conservando la biodiversidad del lugar.</p>		
<p>TIPOS DE GESTIÓN</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> El edificio cuenta con una cubierta verde mejorando la eficiencia energética de la cubierta y habilitando un espacio verde de uso comunitario. → Para la gestión de la cubierta normalmente la comunidad de vecinos subcontrata a una empresa. El edificio cuenta con una fachada verde que mejora la eficiencia energética y el aislamiento del ruido externo, además de singularizar el edificio. → Para la gestión de la fachada normalmente la comunidad de vecinos subcontrata a una empresa. El edificio cuenta con un huerto sobre la cubierta mejorando la eficiencia energética de la cubierta y generando un espacio productivo de uso comunitario. → La gestión del huerto la realizan los propios vecinos. 	<p>Oportunidades</p> <p>Las tendencias externas que se pueden aprovechar (no son acciones) sino valores/situaciones que brindan posibilidades.</p>	<p>Amenazas</p> <p>Las amenazas son tendencias externas sobre las que no tienes control</p>

INFRAESTRUCTURA DE RECARGA DE VEHÍCULOS ELÉCTRICOS Y ALMACENAMIENTO

<p>INTRODUCCIÓN</p> <p>Objetivo: Generar un marco técnico dentro del cual se identificarán Fortalezas, Debilidades, Oportunidades y Amenazas a nivel local y global.</p> <p>Resultado: Identificación de los factores claves positivos y negativos que influyen en el futuro desarrollo del proyecto, así como también sus oportunidades y limitaciones.</p>	<p>Fortalezas</p> <p>Elementos internos basados en los aspectos o beneficios de los recursos existentes</p>	<p>Debilidades</p> <p>Áreas internas o elementos que necesitan mejorarse</p>
<p>INSTRUCCIONES</p> <p>Paso 01: Seleccione un tipo de gestión por equipo</p> <p>Step 02: Toma una nota adhesiva y colócala debajo de las fortalezas, debilidades, oportunidades o amenazas.</p>		
<p>DEFINICIÓN</p> <p>Los vehículos eléctricos necesitan el desarrollo de una red de puntos o estaciones que permita la recarga de estos vehículos. Las baterías de los vehículos ofrecen la posibilidad de utilizar estas mismas para balancear la demanda de la red.</p>		
<p>TIPOS DE GESTIÓN</p> <p>La gestión de la infraestructura la realiza cada propietario al invertir en la instalación de recarga y gestiona personalmente su infraestructura. Cada propietario pide a la Comunidad de Vecinos la instalación de estaciones de recarga del vehículo eléctrico bidireccionales, y es la comunidad la que invierte en la instalación. A cambio la gestión se hace de manera comunitaria, es decir, una empresa subcontratada por la Comunidad de Vecinos se encarga de cargar o utilizar la energía almacenada en el vehículo eléctrico para resolver las necesidades de consumo del edificio.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> El edificio cuenta con preinstalación para la instalación de estaciones de recarga del vehículo eléctrico. → 	<p>Oportunidades</p> <p>Las tendencias externas que se pueden aprovechar (no son acciones) sino valores/situaciones que brindan posibilidades.</p>	<p>Amenazas</p> <p>Las amenazas son tendencias externas sobre las que no tienes control</p>

INFRAESTRUCTURA DE GENERACIÓN DE ENERGÍA RENOVABLE

<p>INTRODUCCIÓN</p> <p>Objetivo: Diseñar un marco técnico dentro del cual se identificarán Fortalezas, Debilidades, Oportunidades y Amenazas a nivel local y global.</p> <p>Resultados: Identificación de los factores claves positivos y negativos que influyen en el futuro desarrollo del proyecto, así como también sus oportunidades y limitaciones.</p>	<p>Fortalezas</p> <p>Elementos internos basados en los aspectos o ventajas de los recursos existentes.</p>	<p>Debilidades</p> <p>Áreas internas o existentes que necesitan mejorarse.</p>
<p>INSTRUCCIONES</p> <p>Paso 01: Seleccione un tipo de gestión por equipo.</p> <p>Step 02: Tome una nota adhesiva y colócala debajo de las fortalezas, debilidades, oportunidades o amenazas.</p>		
<p>DEFINICIÓN</p> <p>Las energías renovables son un tipo de energías derivadas de fuentes naturales que llegan e reponerse más rápido de lo que pueden consumirse. Un ejemplo de estas fuentes son la energía fotovoltaica o la eólica. Estas tecnologías permiten que la energía pueda generarse en el mismo sitio donde se consumen, mejorando la eficiencia energética y reduciendo las pérdidas por distribución.</p>	<p>Oportunidades</p> <p>Los recursos externos que se pueden aprovechar los son recursos o situaciones que brindan posibilidades.</p>	<p>Amenazas</p> <p>Las amenazas son tendencias externas como las que generan crisis.</p>
<p>TIPOS DE GESTIÓN</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. El edificio cuenta con una instalación de paneles fotovoltaicos sobre la cubierta, los cuales permite generar energía renovable. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ La gestión de la infraestructura la realiza la comunidad de vecinos subcontratando a una empresa y repartiendo los beneficios de la energía generada entre los vecinos. La gestión de la infraestructura la realiza la comunidad de vecinos subcontratando a una empresa privada para la gestión de autoconsumo colectivo, venta de energía renovable y compra de energía de los edificios que participan en ella. 2. El edificio cuenta con una instalación de paneles fotovoltaicos sobre la cubierta, incluyendo dicha infraestructura en una comunidad energética renovable. 		

INFRAESTRUCTURA DE GENERACIÓN DE ENERGÍA TÉRMICA

<p>INTRODUCCIÓN</p> <p>Objetivo: Diseñar un marco técnico dentro del cual se identificarán Fortalezas, Debilidades, Oportunidades y Amenazas a nivel local y global.</p> <p>Resultados: Identificación de los factores claves positivos y negativos que influyen en el futuro desarrollo del proyecto, así como también sus oportunidades y limitaciones.</p>	<p>Fortalezas</p> <p>Elementos internos basados en los aspectos o ventajas de los recursos existentes.</p>	<p>Debilidades</p> <p>Áreas internas o existentes que necesitan mejorarse.</p>
<p>INSTRUCCIONES</p> <p>Paso 01: Seleccione un tipo de gestión por equipo.</p> <p>Step 02: Tome una nota adhesiva y colócala debajo de las fortalezas, debilidades, oportunidades o amenazas.</p>		
<p>DEFINICIÓN</p> <p>Los edificios consumen energía para iluminación, ventilación y electrodomésticos, así como para calefacción y refrigeración. En España, se utiliza calderas o bombas de calor individuales para transformar la energía en frío o calor. A pesar de ello, hay otros modelos más eficientes, resumidos en tres categorías para la generación de temperatura en los edificios.</p>	<p>Oportunidades</p> <p>Los recursos externos que se pueden aprovechar los son recursos o situaciones que brindan posibilidades.</p>	<p>Amenazas</p> <p>Las amenazas son tendencias externas como las que generan crisis.</p>
<p>TIPOS DE GESTIÓN</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Generación centralizada por edificio. Este sistema es más eficiente, pero requiere una gestión comunitaria por parte de la Comunidad de Vecinos. 2. Generación a nivel distrito. El cual es el sistema que normalmente suele ser más eficiente. <p>El sistema de generación a nivel distrito plantea 2 alternativas principales de propiedad y gestión:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. La instalación es propiedad de una empresa privada o pública que factura a los usuarios finales por el frío y calor que les entrega. Igual que se factura por la electricidad, el gas o el agua, se factura por el frío o el calor. 2. La instalación es propiedad de los vecinos que están conectados a la red y a través de un contrato de gestión, la gestionan a nivel supracomunidad de vecinos. 		

Appendix 6 – Aarhus LL - AU Viborg Campus Transformation StoryMap

This section presents the interface of the StoryMap adopted for AU Viborg Campus, including how main themes were introduced, in preparation for the Geodesign Workshop.

Link to the StoryMap here: <https://arcg.is/1mniqr>

We want to hear from you!

We invited you to participate in an experimental initiative run by the EU H2020 project PROBONO, that aims to present AU with information that can support them in transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus.

We are an experimental, standalone project that is piloting new ways of engaging with stakeholders in various renovation programmes across Europe. PROBONO is not affiliated in any way with the AU administration nor the Campus Viborg renovation programme.

We want to get your input and views on the transformation and then provide these valuable perspectives to AU and Campus Viborg (unsolicited) with the intention of supporting AU towards an even better transformation outcome.

We kindly ask you to fill out a brief survey after first telling you what we have learnt about the transformation.

*PROBONO is an experimental, standalone project that is piloting new ways of engaging with stakeholders in various renovation programmes across Europe. **PROBONO is not affiliated** in any way with the **AU administration nor the Campus Viborg renovation programme.***

Green Neighbourhood | Probono

Green Building Neighbourhoods PROBONO Vision and Green Building Neighbourhood Transition...

<https://www.probonoh2020.eu/>

AU Viborg Campus

The former Research Station Foulum will be transformed into the **AU Viborg Campus**, which will eventually accommodate around

800 students.

AU Viborg Campus **AU Viborg** is a green campus in Denmark that promotes the green transition in sustainable food, climate-friendly production methods, and bio-based energy solutions through education and research. Its partnership with authorities, society, and businesses enables it to turn its knowledge into practical action.

Main entrance to the Research Centre Foulum

AU Viborg is part of Aarhus University and specialises in food and agriculture research, including plants, animals, food, organic farming, bioenergy, environment, climate, soil, genetics and technology. In **2023**, AU Viborg opens its doors to the **first students in our three new degree programs** in:

- Animal Science
- Plant and food science
- Veterinary medicine

We want to hear from you!

We kindly ask you to fill out a brief three-step survey providing examples of the Research Centre Foulum's existing qualities, challenges, and opportunities.

- Qualities**
 Qualities, is a unique aspect of the Research Centre Foulum that you appreciate and would like to see incorporated into the transformation plan.
- Challenges**
 Challenges that need to be addressed and transformed positively. This challenge could be related to a situation, task, problem, or anything not functioning properly at the Research Centre Foulum.
- Opportunities**
 An opportunity is a potential solution to a previously identified challenge.

Why have you been invited to take part?

We have invited you to participate in this survey because you are a stakeholder who has been involved in transforming the Research Centre Foulum into the AU Viborg Campus, with a high to medium level of involvement.

Taking part in the survey

If you are happy with the information above and are willing to contribute your examples of qualities, challenges and opportunities of the Research Centre Foulum, please complete this Geosurvey. Your responses will be anonymous.

What are the risks of taking part in this research study?

There are no risks of taking part in this study. No personal information will be gathered. All responses are fully anonymous. You can withdraw from the survey at any point before submission by closing the browser or choosing not to submit the form.

The recording below demonstrates the mapping tool participants were invited to use as part of the consultation and includes examples of a **stories and values in Ballina** suggestion being made.

Consent for Participation

Please read the following information carefully and tick the box below.

This form is to assess the qualities, challenges and opportunities of the Research Centre Foulum to transform it into the AU Viborg Campus, as part of **PROBONO** project, funded by the European Commission (EU) Grant Agreement No 101037075. Aarhus is part of the 6 Living Labs that PROBONO has with the aim to Build Green Neighbourhoods.

During this project, we wish to inform you that the information collected from this survey will be made available through the AU

Thank you for actively being part of this dialogue and taking the time to complete this survey!

If you would like more context about the project please explore the following sections.

PROBONO project

Building and renovating in an energy and resource-efficient way

As society becomes increasingly urban and ever dependent on **technological innovations**, it is vital to ensure that **people** and the planet are put at the very heart of this development in a way that is sensitive to and **encourages the protection, expansion or re-introduction of sustainable space** amongst the urban sprawl.

Green Building Neighbourhoods

The concept of **Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN)** in **PROBONO** involves integrating environmentally friendly buildings within specific areas or districts, incorporating **green energy, sustainable transportation, and infrastructure**. This initiative aims to support policies, investments, stakeholder involvement, and behavioural changes to ensure a fair transition while maximizing economic and **social advantages**. Consideration is given to the unique characteristics of each district, such as population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate features.

To learn more about the **H2020 PROBONO** project, click on the following link:

Green Neighbourhood | Probono

Green Building Neighbourhoods PROBONO Vision and Green Building Neighbourhood Transition...

<https://www.probonoh2020.eu/>

Living Labs

PROBONO Living Labs are large-scale, iterative, **open-innovation ecosystems**, operating in a territorial context, **integrating** concurrent **research and innovation** processes within a **public-private-people partnership**.

climate-friendly production methods and fostering close collaboration between education, research, industry, and innovation. Through this synergy, we aim to pave the way for a collective green future that prioritises the well-being of nature, humans, and animals.

Mission

AU Viborg’s mission is to speed up the green transition and prepare the future workforce, aiming to help establish a carbon-neutral society. They emphasise the crucial role of their students and researchers in shaping a sustainable future.

Objectives

- To discuss and explore the views of primary stakeholders (such as people that will be based in Campus Viborg) on making AU Campus Viborg a versatile, sustainable and resilient campus for the students and the community in its surroundings.
- To collate key findings discovered during the workshop and deliver these to AU for their consideration, prepared to support them most effectively.

Domains/Systems

The systems correspond to the probable challenges that the University, Viborg and the surrounding areas can face in the future with the transformation of the AU Viborg campus.

Accessibility

Viborg and Ørum are the nearest towns to DCA. Currently, the transportation methods are buses, trains, private cars and bicycles.

Cycling times

From **Viborg** to **AU Viborg**
42-45 min

From **Ørum** to **AU Viborg**
11-15 min

Public Transport times

From **Viborg** to **AU Viborg**
Bus 17 min
Walking 34 min

From **Ørum** to **AU Viborg**
45-50 min

Train times

From Aarhus to Viborg
1 hr 6 min
 From Randers to Viborg
1 hr 6 min

Results

Qualities Results

Challenges Results

Opportunities Results

How will you find out what happens with this project?

Any updates on the project will be published on the official website and on the landing page

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<https://www.probonoh2020.eu/>

ProbonoH2020

PROBONO is an EU H2020 project and envisions delivering scalable, sustainable and viable zero-carb...

<https://www.youtube.com/@ProbonoH>

PROBONO is a project funded by the European Commission, for more information about **PROBONO project** visit [here](#).

With thanks to our project partners

Contact us:

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AU Viborg Campus | PROBONO

Appendix 7 – Aarhus LL - Geodesign Workshop Agenda.

Agenda AU Viborg Geodesign Workshop

11th April 2024 / 10am-2m @AU Viborg

Time	Activity
9:00 - 9:20	Welcome and introduction to the workshop (Gustaf or Jesper)
9:20 - 9:30	Reviewing survey results on qualities, challenges, and opportunities
9:30 - 10:10	Priorities + Select ideas for the AU Viborg Campus transformation (version 1)
10:10 - 10:30	Presentation of stakeholder group visions
10:30 - 10:50	Select ideas for the AU Viborg Campus transformation (version 2)
10:50 - 11:00	Sociogram
11:00 - 11:30	Negotiation (round 1)
11:30 - 11:45	Break
11:45 - 12:00	Presentation of negotiated visions
12:00 - 12:30	Negotiation (round 2)
12:30 - 13:00	Final discussion
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch

Facilitators:

Joselyn/Philip
Muhammad
Yazan
Sidsel
Tamara

Appendix 8 – Aarhus LL - Feedback Survey from AU Viborg Geodesign Workshop

AU Viborg Geodesign Workshop

PROBONO project and Aarhus University thank you for your participation on the workshop.

In order to collect feedback about the activity's outcomes and to consider potential improvements for future workshop, we invite you to briefly share your experience during the workshop.

joselyn.pelayo@ucd.ie [Switch accounts](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

On scale of 0-10, how likely are you to recommend this event to a friend or colleague? *

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all likely Extremely likely

What is the primary reason for your score? If you have any thoughts or suggestions for improvement, please also share here

Your answer

Select your age group *

- 18 - 25
- 25 - 30
- 30 - 40
- 40 - 50
- 50 - 60
- More than 60

What is your gender *

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

What is your education background? *

- Primary education
- Secondary/high school education
- Vocational school
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree or higher

What is your current occupational status? *

- Paid employed
- Self employed
- Full time student
- Retired
- Unemployed
- Unpaid work
- Stay at home parent
- Unable to work
- Prefer not to say

Please rate the effectiveness of the workshop in enhancing your understanding of Geodesign principles for AU Viborg campus *

- | | | | | | | |
|----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|---------------------|
| | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | |
| Not effective at all | <input type="radio"/> | Extremely effective |

To what extent did the evaluation maps contribute to informed decision-making ^{*} during the Geodesign process for the transformation of AU Viborg Campus?

1 2 3 4 5

Not at all To a large extent

To what extent did GeodesignHub facilitate effective communication and ^{*} collaboration among workshop participants during the Geodesign process for the transformation of the AU Viborg campus?

1 2 3 4 5

Not at all To a large extent

What aspects of the Geodesign workshop did you find most valuable in ^{*} contributing to the development of actions and policies for the transformation of the AU Viborg Campus?

Your answer _____

In your opinion, what improvements or additions could enhance future ^{*} Geodesign workshops with a focus on the transformation of the AU Viborg campus?

Your answer _____

Submit

Clear form